

Faculty for Computer Science, Electrical Engineering and Mathematics
Department of Computer Science
Research Group Secure Software Engineering
Fachgruppe Secure Software Engineering

Master's Thesis

Submitted to the Secure Software Engineering Research Group
in Partial Fulfilment of the Requirements for the Degree of

Master of Science

Evolution of Least-Restrictive Solutions for incomplete Scenario Models

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Paderborn, October 5, 2021

Master's Thesis # MA0225

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am: October 5, 2021

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Abstract. In this thesis, we present an extension for the evolutionary algorithm that Schmelter et al. implemented for the scenario modeling language SML. SML is a modeling language for requirements engineering, in which the system designer can implement and validate reactive black-box behavior for a system by modeling not only the system itself but also the environment (sensors and actors) the system operates in. With their evolutionary algorithm that is able to create new assumptions to add to the SML specification, Schmelter et al. offer an automatic utility to repair incomplete / unrealizable SML specifications. For this generation, they utilize the MOEAFramework, which enables them to search for solutions that are optimal in regards to multiple different objectives. As a new objective, we showcase different metrics to create a notion of *environment restrictiveness*. As a base for that, we were able to utilize multiple graph measures, since we believe that the restrictiveness (or rather the complexity) of an arbitrary SML specification can be represented by its respective state graph. We adjusted and optimized these graph measures to fit our goal of environment restrictiveness and implemented 12 additional different candidates to choose from. After incorporating them into the evolutionary algorithm of Schmelter et al., we evaluated those 12 (and an additional proprietary, already existing) metric candidates with the help of a case study applied on two research examples ("Production Cell" and "EBEAS") to find out which of these metrics is best applicable for our purpose. In the end, we compare the metric candidates in regards to runtime and performance, enabling us to now recommend 3 metrics as good metrics that can all be used for the evolutionary algorithm: $R4$ (the number of distinct decisions, the environment can make when interacting with the system), $R6_S$ (the finite hausdorff dimension of the state graph resembling the SML specification - after adjusting the state graph for super steps) and $R7_S$ (measuring the state graph of the specification for a simplified version of the weakness measure proposed by Cavezza et al. - also after adjusting for super steps). We additionally recommend using $R4$ over the other two metrics, simply because of its superior runtime.

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Introduction

To prepare for presenting our concepts of *restrictiveness* of incomplete scenario models, we first need to simplify our domain of requirements engineering. We utilize this introduction to set boundaries as to where our solution is applicable, as well as to present the problem that we solved. We do this with the help of our running research example taken from literature: "Production Cell". In the end, we present the remaining content of this document and summarize our evaluation results.

1.1 Requirements Engineering and SML

Requirements engineering is a big part of current software development, as not only the concrete implementation but also just the specification of complex systems can be arbitrarily difficult. To be able to easily specify these requirements there have been many different approaches[LDD06] to support the system designer. The approach that we deal with is that of reactive scenario modeling, where, with the help of Domain Specific Languages (DSLs), scenario models can be formally analyzed and automatically validated. More specifically we want to assist in using the Scenario Modeling Language (SML), which is one of these DSLs. The SML enables a requirements engineer to model the behavior of a System under Development (SUD) (e.g. a controller unit in a production cell), by defining its interactions with the environment (e.g. actors and sensors), all while ignoring how the system or the environmental actors actually achieve those behaviors. The requirements engineer just models the so-called "black box" - behavior by specifying what messages the different participants can send to each other and defining how each of the participants has to react to receiving such a message.

SML - Example We explain how SML works with the help of a simple specification for production cells taken from a paper by Gritzner and Greenyer[GG18].

Figure 1.1 shows an assembly line in which blanks get transported via conveyor belts to some destination. During the transportation, the blanks have to be pressed once and the finished plates are then passed on to a deposit belt. The scenario environment consists of an input *table*, an output *deposit belt*, a *press* in the middle, and robotic arms (*arm A* and *arm B*), which move the blanks / plates around. There is also a controller (our SUD), which reacts to messages from the environment sensors and actors and sends commands to them. The scenario starts with blanks arriving at the table. The table sensor notifies the controller of the newly arrived item. The controller then orders arm A to move to the table, pick up the blank, move it to the

Figure 1.1: Production Cell visualization - based on the original by Gritzner and Greenyer.

press, release it and return to its original position. After the blank has arrived at the press, the controller orders the press to press it. When that is done, and the controller has received the corresponding "finished"-message from the press, it tells arm B to move to the press, pick up the finished plate and move it to the deposit belt. In the end, the whole system has taken a blank from the table and created a pressed plate at the deposit belt. The full SML specification for this example can be found in Appendix A.1

The technical aspects of how exactly one can specify such an SML specification are explained in Section 2.6

SML - Problems Although the SML specification is a good utility for the modeling process, it is not quite perfect yet. If the domain and the requirements to specify are sufficiently complex, the requirements engineer is bound to make mistakes at some point, even during the abstract definition process.

We highlight this problem by utilizing our example of a production cell.

Listing 1.1: Guarantee: arms must not collide

```

1  guarantee scenario ArmsMustNotCollideAtPress1 {
2      controller->armA.moveToPress
3      monitored eventually controller->armA.moveToTable
4  } constraints [
5      forbidden controller->armB.moveToPress()
6  ]
7
8  guarantee scenario ArmsMustNotCollideAtPress2 {
9      controller->armB.moveToPress
10     monitored eventually controller->armB.moveToDepositBelt
11 } constraints [
12     forbidden controller->armA.moveToPress()
13 ]

```

The specification contains guarantees (see Listing 1.1) to prevent the collision of our two robotic arms, which could happen if both arms were ordered to move to the press at the same time. The guarantees are specified so that the controller must not order a robotic arm to move to the press if the other robotic arm has already been ordered to move there and has not yet returned.

To give an example where this specification does not suffice, imagine the following sequence of events. After being notified of a new blank plate arriving at the table, the controller orders arm A to pick up the plate from the table and move it to the press (see Figure 1.2). After dropping off the blank plate at the press, the controller orders arm A to move back to the table (see Figure 1.3). Since a blank plate has arrived at the press, it should eventually finish pressing the plate, but it takes significantly long to actually complete the pressing (as is allowed by its assumption Listing 1.2).

Figure 1.2: Production Cell - causing a system violation - Stage 1

Figure 1.3: Production Cell - causing a system violation - Stage 2

Listing 1.2: Assumption: Press presses

```

1  assumption scenario PressActuallyPresses {
2      controller->press.press
3      strict eventually press->controller.pressFinished
4  }

```

Because of this, the controller does not send the command for arm B to move to the press just yet, as this action is only initiated after the press finished the pressing process (see Listing 1.3).

Listing 1.3: Guarantee: React to pressed plate

```

1  guarantee scenario NewPlatePressed {
2      press->controller.pressFinished
3      strict urgent controller->armB.moveToPress
4  }

```

Now a new plate reaches the input table, and the controller commands arm A to pick it up and move it to the press, which arm A does (see Figure 1.4). Then the pressing process is

Figure 1.4: Production Cell - causing a system violation - Stage 3

finally finished, and the controller needs to immediately command arm B to pick up the finished plate (see Figure 1.5). This would cause both arms to be at the press at the same time,

Figure 1.5: Production Cell - causing a system violation - Stage 4

violating the safety guarantee "ArmsMustNotCollideAtPress1". Since the action "controller->armB.moveToPress" is currently forbidden, the controller cannot execute the *strict* and *urgent* command. With this, the environment has found a way to cause the SUD to violate one of its guarantees.

SML - Realizability Checks To find these violations, a specification modeled in SML can be automatically verified by an analysis, based on game theory, proposed by Gritzner and Greenyer. With the *ScenarioTools* framework [GGG⁺17] (an Eclipse-based tooling around SML) they provide tooling for such automatic realizability checks (among other analysis techniques). During the analysis, they generate a state model by putting an environment player against the system player. The environment player can initiate and manipulate event-chains by simulating the behavior of the environmental participants of the specification, while the system player has to react according to their guarantees. The environment player then tries to create environmental situations that force the system into violating any of its guarantees. If the environment can produce a certain event sequence, such that it forces the SUD to violate one of its guarantees (meaning the SUD is not able to fulfill all of its requirements), the specification is called *unrealizable*. We call the corresponding validation process *realizability check*. For our purposes we can define realizability in the following way:

Definition 1.1. An SML specification is called **realizable** if the environment can not produce any sequence of events that would lead to an erroneous state, meaning a state where a system guarantee is violated with certainty.

Analogously an SML specification is called **unrealizable** if the environment can produce such a sequence of events, and force the system to violate one of its guarantees at some point.

When running this realizability check you can export the generated state graph resulting from the analysis. The requirements engineer can utilize this state graph to investigate how the violation could have been provoked and try to figure out a way to fix their specification manually. For example, one could start at an erroneous state and, going backward from that, figure out what chain of events lead to it. For the aforementioned example of the production cell, an excerpt of the state graph resulting from such a game is appended in the appendix Appendix B.

From experience, one can safely assume, that the mistakes relate to the environment, rather than the SUD itself, as requirements engineers tend to miss certain assumptions about the

environment instead of making mistakes in their system guarantees. This leads to the set of assumptions to be *under specified*, meaning there are missing assumptions about the environment. The requirements engineer now needs to find out which assumptions to add to the specification. However, finding the exact assumptions missing is a difficult task on its own, which often requires multiple iterations of updating the specification and running the automatic validation again. This is where the evolutionary generation of assumptions proposed by Schmelter et al. [SGH17] becomes relevant.

1.2 Evolution of new Environment Assumptions

Since specifying the requirements via SML already provides automatic validation by checking the specification for realizability, a logical next step is an automatic assistance in repairing such incomplete specifications. To address this issue, Schmelter et al. [SGH17] presented means to automatically extend an existing, incomplete SML specification. By applying a Multi-objective Evolutionary Algorithm (MOEA)¹ to this problem they generate new assumptions, putting additional constraints on the behavior of environmental actors.

To find out about the MOEAFramework evolution process refer to Section 2.8. In short, the evolution itself is an iterative process, taking the pareto-optimal frontier of the current generation of solutions and evolving a new set of solutions from those. In the end, the presented solutions are then complete in the sense, that the environmental actors / events can no longer force the SUD to violate any of its guarantees - the system is no longer *unrealizable*. Since there exist multiple possible solutions for any given incomplete scenario, and due to the inherent non-deterministic approach of the MOEAFramework, the algorithm by Schmelter et al. generates multiple different solutions for any presented specification, where some of those might be more useful than others, depending on the evaluation. To compute the pareto front Schmelter et al. configured the algorithm to evaluate 3 numerical objectives, which the framework can easily compare and optimize for minimal objective values. Schmelter et al. currently use three optimization goals.

- **Evolved Assumption Size** The overall number of newly generated assumptions. This is a minimization value. It is used to choose simple, small solutions over complicated big ones.
- **Environment related proportion** This number is obtained by dividing the number of generated messages for the environment by the number of all generated messages (SUD and environment). This is supposed to be maximized, as it is believed, that information about the environment is missing, rather than information about the SUD.
- **Restrictiveness-Penalty** Newly generated scenarios get assigned a penalty value for their restrictiveness. *Strict* messages lead to higher penalties than regular ones. *Committed* messages get assigned a higher value than *eventually* messages. By minimizing this penalty, the generator tries to reduce the impact on the environment of a new solution. This is a highly local approach. Penalties for solutions are evaluated by summing up the penalties of the generated scenarios, which in turn are evaluated by how urgent and strict the newly evaluated fragments / messages are.

A fitness function assigns a numerical value for each of these goals to the generated solutions, enabling the algorithm to select a set of *pareto-optimal* (see Section 2.8.1) solutions by comparing / sorting for these optimization values. The pareto front of each iteration is then used for further

¹They use the MOEAFramework[Had12] (<https://github.com/MOEAFramework/MOEAFramework>), which provides a java toolkit for implementing multi-objective optimization algorithms.

evolution during the generation process and the final pareto front at the end is then presented to the requirements engineer. The requirements engineer can then choose the "best" solution as they see fit.

1.3 Problem Statement

During the evolution of new assumptions, Schmelter et al. utilize a penalty value for restrictiveness, which they want to minimize to keep the evolutionary algorithm from over-specifying the environment, as this would reduce the applicability of the specification in real-world settings. This "old" objective for restrictiveness is evaluated by calculating individual penalty values for the newly generated scenarios, based on the occurrence of certain model elements, and combining them. One could thus say that this definition of restrictiveness is *local*. The problem that we want to address is that in many cases there still exist a multitude of solutions scoring the same values on all of these objectives. This means that the "old" local definition is not sufficient to capture the desired restrictiveness. We show an example, where this local definition can not distinguish between two solutions where one is less restrictive than the other.

Example We are again making use of the "ProductionCell" example from before, where rapidly incoming new plates can trigger a system violation if the pressing is not finished in time.

Listing 1.4: Solution A

```

1 // safety assumptions (sample solution A)
2 assumption scenario BlanksArriveSlowly{
3     tableSensor->controller.blankArrived
4     monitored eventually controller->armB.releasePlate
5 } constraints [
6     forbidden tableSensor->controller.blankArrived()
7 ]

```

Listing 1.5: Solution B

```

1 // safety assumptions (sample solution B)
2 assumption scenario BlanksArriveSlowly{
3     tableSensor->controller.blankArrived
4     monitored eventually controller->armB.pickUp
5 } constraints [
6     forbidden tableSensor->controller.blankArrived()
7 ]

```

The generated sample solutions A and B (see Listing 1.4 and Listing 1.5) show two different new assumptions, that would both individually solve the original issue. Both solutions prevent the environment from "sending new plates" before the old one has been pressed by the press and retrieved by the robotic arm B.

Both of these solutions perform equally well on all of the current objectives (see Table 1.1). However, the two solutions have a different impact on the environment, as one restricts it further than the other. If we observe the state graphs, we can see a significantly smaller graph for solution A compared to solution B (see Figure B.2 and Figure B.3), which means that in this specification there are fewer possible states and sequences of events, that can occur. As the only difference between the two specifications are the newly generated assumptions, we can deduce, that these new assumptions restrict the environment to different degrees (solution A restricts it further).

To generalize the problem highlighted by the example: There are currently many different valid solutions, which can be evolved with the same objective values, despite imposing different grades of restrictiveness on the environment.

Table 1.1: Objective Scores of Solutions A and B

	"Size"	Environment related proportion	"Restrictiveness-Penalty"
Solution A	3	0.33	0.1
Solution B	3	0.33	0.1

The table shows the different scores each solution achieved for the different objectives.

- **Size** = 3 (number of evolved fragments / messages) * 1 (number of evolved scenarios) * 1 (standard deviation of fragments/scenario + 1)
- **Environment related proportion** = 1 - environment relation = $1 - 2/3 = 0.33$.
- **Restrictiveness-Penalty** = 0.1, since each solution does not contain strict messages and only contains one forbidden constraint and one non-eventually message.

1.4 Contributions and Outline

To combat the problem described in Section 1.3, we propose to change or extend the definition of the restrictiveness optimization goal or add a new optimization goal for global environment restrictiveness. This *global* definition has to take into account the resulting state space of the specification. We believe that this solution can either replace or at least serve as an extension to the local definition and support it. We start by reintroducing certain concepts and definitions (see Chapter 2) and presenting some related work (see Chapter 3) to provide context for our solutions.

In the following (see Chapter 4) we present our approach towards solving the problem of environment restrictiveness. For this, we present multiple metrics to be applied to the specification (and its state graph) as a whole, which can be used to compare different evolved scenarios. Since not all of these metrics consist of simple numeric values, we also show how we extended the MOEAFramework[Had12] so that we could specify general comparable objectives. We also present different adjustments, which can be made to the state graph of a given specification, to reduce its information content to the restrictiveness of just the environment and not the system too.

We use a case study[KBP11] based on two research examples ("Production Cell" and "EBEAS") to find correlations between the different metrics and evaluate what definitions and implementations are the most effective. We present our findings in regards to runtime and quality of the generated solutions in Chapter 5. Interestingly enough, the "Super Steps" is not recommended for all of the metrics, but just the more complex ones, where it drastically decreases the necessary runtime for calculating the metric. At the end of that chapter, we explain why we recommend using $R4$ (the decision power of the environment) as the metric for restrictiveness, and, that other metrics ($R6_S$ and $R7_S$) perform equally well, but take up just a little more time.

After that, we propose some ideas for where future research could improve our current findings and what new ideas we believe are worth investigating (see Chapter 6).

In the end, we conclude and summarize our work once more.

1.4 CONTRIBUTIONS AND OUTLINE

We use the foundations chapter to reintroduce certain concepts and methods to provide the technical background necessary to follow this paper. With this, we attempt to get everyone on the same page and prevent misunderstandings.

2.1 Formal Languages

We present the definitions for different types of languages as they are commonly used in the literature.

Definition 2.1. An Alphabet Σ is a set of literals (e. g. $\Sigma = \{a, b, c\}$).

Definition 2.2. A Word $w \in \Sigma^*$ is a finite concatenation of literals from a given alphabet (e. g. $w = a \cdot b \cdot a$ or in short $w = aba$).

We often use w_i to identify the literal at position i in the word w . For example, if the word w is defined as $w = abc$, then the literal at index 2 is defined as $w_2 = c$.

The length of a word w is written as $\text{len}(w)$ or $|w|$.

Concatenation is defined not only over literals but words too, such that the word $u = v \cdot w$ is defined as $u_i = v_i \ \forall i \in [0, |v| - 1]$ and $u_{i+|v|} = w_i \ \forall i \in [0, |w| - 1]$ (e. g. $v = aba; w = cbc; u = vw = abacbc$).

Definition 2.3. A Language L is defined as a set of words over an alphabet Σ . It is constrained by the set of all words that could possibly be defined over this alphabet ($L \subseteq \Sigma^*$). We say a Language accepts or contains a word w , if $w \in L$.

For most purposes finite definitions for these concepts suffice. In the case of infinite length words, we analogously define ω - languages.

Definition 2.4. An ω (omega) - word w is a concatenation of literals from a given alphabet (similar to Definition 2.2).

In contrast to a regular word, an ω - word is of infinite length.

Due to this, concatenation has to be restricted. An ω - word w can only be on the right hand side of concatenation, never on the left.

In the context of ω - words it is difficult to investigate the structure or properties of a given word due to it's infinite length.

To alleviate this we will often look into the prefix of an ω - word. We define a fixed length prefix $\text{pref}_n(w) = w_0 \cdot w_1 \cdots w_{n-1}$.

The set of all prefixes of all lengths is defined as $\text{pref}(w) := \{\text{pref}_i(w) \mid i \in \mathbb{N}\}$.

Definition 2.5. An ω - Language L is defined as a set of ω - words (see Definition 2.4) over an alphabet Σ . It is constrained by the set of all ω - words that could possibly be defined over this alphabet ($L \subseteq \Sigma^*$).

Like for original languages, we say an ω - Language accepts or contains an ω - word w , if $w \in L$. Analogously to Definition 2.4 we define $\text{pref}_n(L)$ as the set of all possible prefixes of length n of words in L .

2.2 Automata

For many languages one can construct *automata* that can, given a word w , decide if w is contained in L . If the automaton decides that a word is part of L it *accepts* w . If such an automaton exists for a given language, the language is called *regular*. For any finite language L , there exists a Deterministic Finite Automaton (DFA) [KN12] that accepts it. For ω -languages 2.5 one has to make some augmentations to deal with infinity. To this extent one can construct a Deterministic Muller Automaton (DMA) [Mul63].

Definition 2.6. A Deterministic Muller Automaton (DMA) is a tuple $M := (\Omega, \Sigma, q_0, \delta, F)$. Ω is the set of possible states in M . Σ is the alphabet over which the DMA operates. $q_0 \in \Omega$ is the initial state of the automaton. $\delta : \Omega \times \Sigma \implies \Omega$ is a Set of transitions of the form q_i, a, q_j , where $q_i, q_j \in \Omega$ and $a \in \Sigma$. F is a set of Muller conditions f_i , where a single condition consists of multiple states ($f_i \subseteq \Omega$).

When the automaton checks an ω - word w , it reads the literals in order and applies the corresponding transitions, as defined in δ . By doing so, different states are visited infinitely often. We call this set of infinitely visited states S . A Muller condition f_i counts as satisfied if all of its states are contained in S and vice versa ($f_i = S$). To accept a word w , at least one of the Muller conditions has to be satisfied.

In addition to the Muller automata and Muller conditions, with their strict equality, a different type of automaton has also been defined.

Definition 2.7. A Deterministic Büchi Automaton (DBA) is a tuple $M := (\Omega, \Sigma, q_0, \delta, B)$. Analogously to Definition 2.6, Ω, Σ, q_0 and δ capture the possible states, the alphabet, the initial state, and the set of possible transitions.

The working mechanism of the Büchi automaton also matches that of Definition 2.6. A word is checked by gradually invoking the transitions as required by the next literal in the word.

The difference shows in B . For a DBA B is a single set of accepting states. It is also called the Büchi condition. In contrast to a Muller condition f_i (in which the accepting states have to be equal to the infinitely often visited states S (defined exactly like for the DMA case)), the Büchi condition B is satisfied, if at least one of the states in B is also in S ($B \cap S \neq \emptyset$).

This definition restricts the acceptance criteria to a single Büchi condition. For some applications, multiple such conditions are required to hold.

Definition 2.8. The Deterministic Generalized Büchi Automaton (DGBA) is defined similar to the DBA. The only difference is again in B , the acceptance condition. For a DGBA we define B as a set of multiple Büchi conditions (so now B is a set of sets of states), which all have to hold to accept a word. Meaning that for every Büchi condition (set of states) at least one state has to be in the set of states that are visited infinitely often (S) ($\forall B_i | \exists b \in B_i b \in S$).

Equivalence Any DGBA can be transformed into a *regular* DBA. Any *regular* DBA can be translated to an equivalent DMA by keeping the set of states Ω , initial state q_0 , the transitions δ and setting the set of Muller conditions as $F := \{f_i | f_i \in 2^Q \wedge f_i \cap B \neq \emptyset\}$. By this, we construct the Muller conditions, so that the automaton accepts a word exactly when the set of infinitely visited states contains at least one of the Büchi acceptance states.

Representation as Graphs All of these automata can be represented by graphs. We use these to identify the restrictiveness of a given automaton and thus the restrictiveness of the corresponding SML specification.

2.3 Graphs

The state space for our SML specification can be reduced to a simple unweighted graph. As such, it helps to reintroduce graph theory as well. We start by covering textbook standards [HHN⁺65].

2.3.1 Basics on Graphs

Definition 2.9. A directed graph G consists of two sets V, E , where V is the set of so called nodes and E is the set of edges, which are tuples of nodes ($e \in E := (v_1, v_2), v_1 \in V, v_2 \in V$).

Definition 2.10. A Graph can be undirected, in which case any edge is just a 2-set of nodes instead of a tuple ($e \in E := \{v_1, v_2\}, v_1 \in V, v_2 \in V$). Here the edge is equivalent to two directed edges $e_1 = (v_1, v_2)$ and $e_2 = (v_2, v_1)$.

Definition 2.11. A Graph can be a weighted graph, in which case any edge is assigned a numerical value called edge-weight.

$$w(e) = n \in \mathbb{R}$$

These weights can be used to e. g. assign penalties for taking a certain edge while traversing the graph or to determine a more refined version of distance between nodes.

An unweighted graph can be interpreted as a weighted graph where all edge-weights are 1.

Definition 2.12. A Path $p \in V^n$ in our graph is an ordered set of nodes $(v_1, v_2, \dots, v_l, v_{l+1}, \dots, v_n)$, where for each pair of neighboring nodes there exists an edge in G
 $\forall i \in [0, n - 1] \exists e = (v_i, v_{i+1}) \in E$

Definition 2.13. The length of a path is the summed up weight of all the edges that are part of that path.

$$l(p) = \sum_{e \in E(p)} w(e), \text{ where } E(p) \text{ denotes the edges contained in } p.$$

Definition 2.14. A Cycle in our graph is a path, where the first and last node are equal ($v_1 = v_n$)

Definition 2.15. The distance between two nodes is the minimal length of a path connecting them.

$$d(v_a, v_b) = \min_{p \in P'} l(p) \tag{2.1}$$

where $P' := \{p \in P | p \text{ starts at } v_a \text{ and ends at } v_b\}$.

Definition 2.16. The diameter of a graph G is the maximum distance of two nodes in G .

$$D(G) = \max_{v_a, v_b \in G} d(v_a, v_b) \tag{2.2}$$

Definition 2.17. A clique is a special graph where there is a direct edge from any one node to any other node.

$$\forall v_a, v_b \in V \exists e = (v_a, v_b) \in E$$

Definition 2.18. An adjacency matrix is a representation for a graph G , that provides useful information about its connectivity. The adjacency matrix is a square matrix $A^{n \times n}$ where n is equal to the number of states / nodes in G ($n = |V(G)|$). A single entry $A_{(i,j)}$ of the adjacency matrix is 1 iff there is an Edge from Q_i to Q_j in G ($\exists e \in E(G) | e = (Q_i, Q_j)$). Otherwise the value is 0.

Definition 2.19. A distance matrix contains even more information about the graph than the adjacency matrix. Here, instead of a binary value of 0 or 1, the value of any entry $A_{(i,j)}$ is defined by the minimum number of steps needed to get from state Q_i to Q_j . This distance matrix is very useful for the computation of our graph metrics.

2.4 LTL formulae

Linear Temporal Logic (LTL)[BKL08, Chapter 5] is an extension of boolean algebra[Goo07]. For every LTL formula (Φ), there exists an ω - language (see Definition 2.5) $L(\Phi)$, which contains all the ω - words satisfying Φ . Apart from the usual boolean logical operators (\wedge, \vee, \neg), there are additional temporal operators to introduce the concept of certain conditions holding only for a limited duration. These additional operators are F (finally / eventually), G (globally / always), X (next), U (until), R (release), W (weak until) and M (strong release). All of these operators are only concerned with the future (the remaining part of the word, including the current letter). To find out if an ω - word satisfies an LTL formula, it has to satisfy these new operators as well. To explain how they work, let $w = w_0w_1w_2 \dots$ where w^i denotes the suffix of w starting at positions w_i . The temporal operators then work as follows:

- **F** An ω - word w^i satisfies a formula of the form $F\Phi$ iff $\exists j \geq i : w^j$ (the rest of the word starting from any point in the future or immediately) satisfies Φ . In some literature, \diamond is used as an alternative notation for the X operator.
- **G** An ω - word w^i satisfies a formula of the form $G(\Phi)$ iff $\forall j \geq i : w^j$ satisfies Φ . The G operator can also be encoded as $\neg F \neg \Phi$ (there is no point in the future in which Φ is violated). In some literature, \square is used as an alternative notation for the X operator.
- **X** An ω - word w^i satisfies a formula of the form $X\Phi$ iff w^{i+1} (the rest of the word starting from the next step) satisfies Φ . In some literature, \bigcirc is used as an alternative notation for the X operator.
- **U** An ω - word w^i satisfies a formula of the form $\Psi U \Phi$ iff $\exists j \geq i : w^j$ satisfies Φ and $\forall i \leq k < j : w^k$ satisfies Ψ .
- **R** An ω - word w^i satisfies a formula of the form $\Psi R \Phi$ iff $\exists j \geq i : w^j$ satisfies Ψ and w^i satisfies Φ . In a sense, this is to the until operator U, what the always operator G is to the eventually operator F.
- **W and M** The weak until and strong release operators are extended variations of the until and release operator. They are not always defined (like in this thesis), as they can be reduced to a combination of existing simpler operators.

Fairness Conditions If a sub formula consists only of conjunctions, using operators G and F , we call it a *Fairness Condition*. In total there are 3 types of fairness conditions.

- **unconditional** An unconditional fairness condition is specified as $fair_u = G(F(\Phi))$.
- **strong** A strong fairness condition is specified as $fair_s = G(F(\Psi) \implies G(F(\Phi)))$.
- **weak** A weak fairness condition is specified as $fair_w = F(G(\Psi) \implies G(F(\Phi)))$.

When talking about fairness conditions in general one usually means a conjunction over fairness conditions of any type ($fair = fair_u \wedge fair_s \wedge fair_w$).

2.5 GR(1) Specifications

GR(1) formulae, or formulae of *generalized reactivity(1)*[BJP⁺12] describe a subset of LTL formulae, which consist only of the original boolean operators and the additional temporal operators: X , G , F . The operators U , R , W , M are not used. Additionally, GR(1) formulae have to show a certain structure. With GR(1) formulae you specify assumption \implies guarantee behavior of the form $(G(F\Phi_1) \wedge G(F\Phi_2) \dots) \implies (G(F\Psi_1) \wedge G(F\Psi_2) \dots)$. This formula can contain three different types of conditions, which are connected as a conjunction.

- **initial conditions** Pure boolean conjunctions over the variables, that set up the initial state of the system and the environment.
- **invariants** Transitions of the form $G(\phi_1 \implies X\phi_2)$, that specify required reactive behavior according to LTL logic.
- **unconditional fairness conditions** A conjunction of conditions of the form $GF(\phi)$, which resemble the fact that the system has to enter certain states eventually.

GR(1) specifications are used for automatic model checking on specifications.

2.5.1 Special Attributes

To enable a constructive discussion about GR(1) specifications we introduce certain attributes as they are used in the literature.

Definition 2.20. A GR(1) specification is called *realizable* if there is no way for the environment to force the system to violate any of its guarantees.

Definition 2.21. A GR(1) specification is called *well-separated* if there is no way for the system to force the environment to violate any of its guarantees. As Klein and Pnueli [KP11] presented, this can even be checked independently from the system. The set of environment assumptions is *non-well-separated* iff any system can force the environment to violate its assumptions. This means that the initial condition, the invariant, and the fairness condition of the environment all have to be satisfied under any circumstances.

2.6 Scenario Modeling Language

As explained in the Section 1.1, SML is one possible notation to specify requirements for a concrete system. One of the most important advantages of SML is, that it is a special extended form of GR(1) specifications. As such it supports automated model checking by nature.

2.6.1 Content / Syntax

We want to use this section to give a summary of how a requirements engineer can formulate the desired behavior of the system and its expected environment in SML. The SML language contains many helpful structures to set up a specification.

Actors An engineer first models the actors that take part in the specification. In Listing 2.1 you can see the specified actors for the environment (*armA*, *armB*, *press*, *tableSensor*) and the actor that corresponds to the SUD.

Listing 2.1: Example Actors - ProductionCell

```

1  static role Controller controller
2  static role ArmA armA
3  static role ArmB armB
4  static role Press press
5  static role TableSensor tableSensor

```

Messages / Events Each actor is then configured to provide certain events, which can be invoked via messages from other actors. As an example we point towards Listing 2.2, where the *controller* invokes event *moveToPress* on the *armA*. These events correspond to the alphabet Σ of the ω - language, that resembles the specification. If such a message is sent, it can trigger so called *scenarios*.

Listing 2.2: Example Scenario - ProductionCell

```

1  guarantee scenario ArmsMustNotCollideAtPress1 {
2      controller->armA.moveToPress
3      monitored eventually controller->armA.moveToTable
4  } constraints [
5  forbidden controller->armB.moveToPress()
6  ]

```

Scenarios Here we distinguish between two types of scenarios. *System guarantees* are scenarios that define the behavior of the system. These represent the requirements for the system to fulfill, which can then later be implemented by a developer. Each of these guarantees consists of some sort of trigger, that activates the scenario. In addition, each guarantee can contain constraints that forbid certain behavior, thus limiting the possible options for the system as long as the scenario is active. Each guarantee also contains one or multiple actions or messages, that can be specified to be executed either immediately or eventually. The last of these actions release the scenario and close it, allowing the system to perform the formerly forbidden actions again.

Apart from these system guarantees, one also models *environment assumptions*, which specify how environmental actors can interact with the system in a similar manner. Together these assumptions and guarantees resemble a specification for a real-world system and reduce it to a set of event sequences that can occur and invoke each other. In our example Listing 2.2 the scenario that is triggered is the system guarantee *ArmsMustNotCollideAtPress1*.

2.6.2 Relation to GR(1) formulae

In general, SML specifications are a variation of GR(1) - formulae which in turn are just a subset of LTL. Here the alphabet which the corresponding formula works with (and which the resulting ω - language is defined over) corresponds to the messages / events 2.6.1, that can be sent to the actors. The different possible sequences of events, that are allowed in a given SML specification, can then be interpreted as words in the ω - language. The scenarios 2.6.1 correspond to invariants to be interpreted in the GR(1) formula. As fairness conditions for the

system player in the GR(1) game, a message has to be sent by the environment at some point in time (always eventually). In the resulting DBA this corresponds to the environment-controlled states, which have to be picked as a set of satisfying states S as Büchi condition. This means, that eventually the system will have completed its invariant requirements and the environment can interact again. This fairness condition prevents the system from never completely fulfilling its requirements.

The close relation to GR(1) specifications makes it possible to construct a DBA for the SML specification, describing its behavior. Ultimately this allows for the creation of a graph, that resembles the possible behavior and enables us to analyze the complexity and structure of the specification, with the help of that graph. We give an example for that with Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Extract from state graph - Production Cell with Solution A

This figure shows an extract from the state graph of the production cell example.

In Figure 2.1 you can see part of the state graph, that represents the possible event chains in the "Production Cell" example when applying the solution A presented in Section 1.3. You can see the different graph nodes / states, that arise from different simultaneously active scenarios. For example, the node / state "12" contains the active scenarios "BlanksArriveSlowly", "PressActuallyPresses" and "ArmAArrivesAtTable". From this state, two possible events can happen.

1. Arm A arrives at the table before the press finishes pressing the plate. It sends the corresponding message to the controller (`armA->controller.arrivedAtTable()`) and the state

can be switched from "12" to "13". There the scenario "ArmAArrivesAtTable" is no longer active.

2. The press finishes pressing the plate before arm A arrives at the table. The press sends the corresponding message to the controller (`press→controller.pressFinished()`) and the state changes to state "20". Here, the scenario "PressActuallyPresses", which has been completed/released by the message, is no longer active. Additionally, a new scenario has become active, which was triggered by the message; "NewPlatePressed".

If the second option is taken, we have a special case. In state "20" there is a system guarantee (S) active, to which the system has to react immediately (refer to Appendix A.1). The controller has to send a message to arm B "`controller→armB.moveToPress()`", which causes a switch to the next state ("21"), where the critical system guarantee was fulfilled and new guarantees and assumptions become active.

As we can see in this graph there might be multiple options for the environment to choose from, which we want to preserve as much as possible to achieve a minimum environment restrictiveness. With the state graph at hand, we can construct different metrics describing the restrictiveness of the environment (or the system respectively), by measuring its freedom of choice.

2.7 Strength / Complexity Measures

There have been some approaches to measure the strength / complexity of arbitrary graphs. We showcase these measures, as we utilize them as a base and build upon them to find good metric candidates for environmental restrictiveness in SML graphs. We introduce the mechanics of these graph theoretical measures and what their purpose is.

Implication When given two graphs we can determine a simple ordering of complexity / restrictiveness, iff one of the graphs completely contains the other.

Definition 2.22. *We say a graph G implies (or extends) another graph G' iff the set of states of G contains all states of G' ($V(G) \supset V(G')$) and the set of transitions in G contains all of the transitions of G' as well ($E(G) \supset E(G')$).*

It's obvious, that in the case of implication all possible decisions in G' can also be made in G . If anything, G offers extended decisions or entirely new ones. With that in mind, we can safely say, that G' is at least as restrictive as G , if not even more restrictive. Sadly, implication can only serve as a metric for restrictiveness if one graph directly implies another. In general, this does not have to be the case, which is why we need to find a more independent definition for restrictiveness. Nonetheless, implication can serve as a base level for validation of our metrics. If an implication relation holds between two graphs G and G' , such that G implies G' , then our restrictiveness metric should always prefer G over G' (assign a higher restrictiveness value to G). If we find a metric, that ranks G as more restrictive than G' , despite G implying G' , then we can conclude, that the metric is flawed.

Entropy Entropy has been a measure for an *amount of information* contained in many contexts so far. The probably most well-known and fundamental version being the "Shannon-Entropy" [Sha48].

In their paper [WCT⁺19] Wan et al. present a variation of entropy to be used as a measure for the information contained in general graphs. With this Wan et al. hope to capture the

complexity of any given graph. To prepare for the definition of entropy given by Wan et al. we first need to introduce additional definitions for certain concepts in graph theory.

Definition 2.23. *The set of acyclic sub graphs in G is defined as all sub graphs G' of G where there is no path in G' that has the same beginning and end node:*

$$SF(G) := \{(V', E') \in G \mid V' \subset V, \neg \exists p \in P, first(p) = last(p) \wedge \forall v \in p, v \in V'\} \quad (2.3)$$

Definition 2.24. *The amount of acyclic sub graphs in G of size k is defined as:*

$$S_k(G) = |\{G' \in SF(G) \mid |V(G')| = k\}| \quad (2.4)$$

Definition 2.25. *The total amount of acyclic sub graphs in G is defined as:*

$$S(G) = \sum_{k=1}^n S_k(G) \quad (2.5)$$

Definition 2.26. *Using these definitions Wan et al. define the entropy H of a graph of size n :*

$$H(G) = - \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{S_k(G)}{S(G)} \log\left(\frac{S_k(G)}{S(G)}\right) \quad (2.6)$$

This formula puts a value on the growth rate of the number of acyclic sub graphs of size k for increasing k . How we intend to apply this measure on SML specifications is explained in Section 4.2.3

Finite Hausdorff Dimension The hausdorff measure is a utility to capture how many different possibilities one has for continuing a word in any formal language. When transferred to graphs / state spaces, this describes the amount of different possible edges / transitions from one node / state to others. However, the original hausdorff measure works on infinite metric spaces and has a value of 0 on finite ones. Since we are working on finite metric spaces with our SML specifications, this regular hausdorff measure is useless if applied directly.

An adjustment, called "finite hausdorff dimension", was proposed in [Alo16] by Juan M. Alonso. It enables the application of the hausdorff measure on simple finite graphs.

Definition 2.27. *The author defines the finite hausdorff dimension of such a graph as:*

$$dim_f(G) = \frac{\ln(v(G))}{\ln(D(G))} \quad (2.7)$$

where $D(G)$ is the Diameter of G as defined in Definition 2.16, and where $v(G)$ is the "vertex clique covering number" of the graph G as defined in Definition 2.28

Definition 2.28. *The vertex clique covering number $v(G)$ is defined as the minimum number of cliques, taken from subgraphs of G , required to collect the entirety of $G = (V, E)$.*

$$v(G) = \min |C(G)|, \forall v \in V, \exists c \in C(G), v \in c \quad (2.8)$$

where $C(G)$ is a set of cliques $\{c_1, \dots, c_m\}$ in G .

In Section 4.2.4 we apply this to the state graph created from SML specifications.

Weakness (Cavezza et al.) The weakness measure presented by Cavezza et al (see Section 3.1) serves as a possible base for our restrictiveness metric candidates.

While their approach is more general, we believe that it can be applied to SML as well, as SML serves as a natural extension of GR(1) specifications for guarantee/assumption scenarios. We believe that this weakness measure can provide a promising definition of restrictiveness, that we implement and investigate in this thesis. In Section 4.2.5 we show how we adjusted the weakness measure for the evolutionary generation.

2.8 MOEAFramework

The MOEAFramework [Had12] provides java libraries for setting up an evolutionary generation of solutions, which has to be configured according to the developer's needs. The evolution itself consists of several iterations. Each iteration begins with generating a set of new solutions (in our case extending the existing specification by additional assumptions). These new solutions get created by augmenting existing solutions from the previous generation or just coming up with random new solutions. After the generation process, these solutions get evaluated according to the specified objectives and constraints. With the classical MOEAFramework, these have to be numeric values in order for the regular compare-operations to be able to interpret the objectives correctly. With our extension *MOEAFramework_GeneralExtension* (see Section 4.5) we extended this behavior to allow for custom data types as objectives, as long as a matching comparator is given as well. The MOEAFramework then uses these objectives (and constraints) to compute a pareto front (see Section 2.8.1) from the evolved candidates of the current iteration. This pareto front is then used as a base for the next generation of solutions. After the final iteration, the pareto front can be presented to the user to choose the best solution from, as they see fit. To get to this final iteration, the MOEAFramework can be configured to take into account the constraints, so that it can put out only realizable solutions for example.

2.8.1 Pareto-Optimality

Since pareto optimality is a central topic in multi-objective optimization, we take this opportunity to re-introduce the theoretical concept.

Definition 2.29. *A single entry E out of a data set is called pareto-optimal, if there exists no other entry E' in that set, that outperforms or at least matches E by every measure.*

Definition 2.30. *A pareto-frontier (or pareto front) is the set of pareto-optimal entries out of a given data set.*

To give an example: In a setting of data points $\{A = (2,2), B = (2,1), C = (1,2.1), D = (1.9, 0.2), E = (1,1), F = (1.5, 1.9), G = (0.8, 2)\}$, where we want to minimize the optimization values 1 and 2, the *pareto-frontier* consists of the data points $\{D,E,G\}$, as shown in Figure 2.2.

2.9 Statistics

To support our evaluation we also need to provide some basic explanations for the statistical tests we used.

Figure 2.2: Example for a *pareto frontier* of minimal values.

2.9.1 Kendall's Tau

Kendall's τ [Puk11] is a measurement to find correlation / agreement between different rankings. The test assigns a τ -coefficient to any pair of two rankings. This τ -coefficient is a real number in the range of $[-1, 1]$, where a value of 1 resembles a perfect correlation (agreement) and a value of -1 resembles a perfect inverse correlation (disagreement). A value of 0 hints at independence between the two rankings.

Given a data set, it checks if two rankings / metrics would display the same preference over every pair of entries in that data set.

1. Both metrics ranking A higher than B / preferring A over B
2. Both metrics ranking A lower than B / preferring B over A
3. Both rankings assigning the same value to A and B / showing no preference

If neither of those is true, then the two measurements have a different preference in regards to this specific pair of entries.

Given a data set of n entries, there are $\binom{n}{2} = \frac{n*(n-1)}{2}$ possible pairs of entries. A preference decision has to be made by a ranking / measurement candidate for each of those.

Definition 2.31. *Given the number of equal preferences n_1 and the number of different preferences n_2 for two rankings, the τ - coefficient of those rankings is defined as:*

$$\tau = \frac{n_1 - n_2}{\binom{n}{2}} = \frac{n_1 - n_2}{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}} = \frac{2 * (n_1 - n_2)}{n(n-1)} \quad (2.9)$$

2.9.2 Kendall Tau - test

To make a decisive claim about two metrics, one can of course not simply post a high Kendall τ - coefficient and claim correlation. We have to argue for statistical significance. To do this, the Kendall τ test incorporates the size of the data sample. For this statistical test, you choose the null hypothesis "metric A and metric B are independent". The distribution over the Kendall τ coefficient then has a mean value of 0. Since this distribution does not match any commonly

used distribution (e. g. normal distribution) it is usually approximated by a normal distribution with a mean value of $\mu = 0$ and a standard deviation of $\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{2(2n+5)}{9n(n-1)}}$. This approximation is generally accepted to be close enough for larger samples ($n > 20$).

This enables us to utilize the regular z-score for the normal distribution (95% confidence interval \rightarrow z-score of 1.96, 99% confidence interval \rightarrow z-score of 2.58). This means that, if the null hypothesis were to be true and the metrics were in fact independent, with 99.9% confidence, the Kendall τ coefficient would be in the range of $[-2.58 * \sqrt{\frac{4n+10}{(9n^2-9n^1)*n}}, 2.58 * \sqrt{\frac{4n+10}{(9n^2-9n)*n}}]$.

Related Work

3.1 "A Weakness Measure for GR(1) formulae"

In their paper[CAG18], Cavezza et al. present a new measure to compare different GR(1) formulae. This weakness measure can give insight into the weakness of a language created by any given GR(1) formulae.

While their approach is more general, we believe that it can be applied to SML as well, since SML serves as a natural extension of GR(1) formulae for guarantee/assumption scenarios.

In their paper, they lament the missing attention brought to the weakness of environment assumptions and mention, that current algorithms only use direct implication as a substitute measure for weakness.

They present entropy and hausdorff dimension as better measurements for weakness but show that, despite satisfying the implication requirement, neither of these suffice to present a complete ordering over different GR(1) specifications.

They propose, that for creating such an ordering, one can define the weakness of a GR(1) specification G as $W(G)$ as a tuple of hausdorff dimensions, by applying the hausdorff dimension on the original language ϕ , as well as its fairness complement ϕ^c . We refer to the hausdorff dimension of the fairness complement as *hausdorff complement*. The resulting tuple $(w_1 = \dim(\phi), w_2 = \dim(\phi^c))$ can then give insight into what the GR(1) formula is capable of producing, as well as what it's not capable of producing. A GR(1) formula G where $W(G) = (w_1, w_2)$ is then weaker than another GR(1) formula G' with $W(G') = (w'_1, w'_2)$ iff either $w_1 < w'_1$ or $w_1 = w'_1 \wedge w_2 > w'_2$. This measurement enables Cavezza et al. to rank two different GR(1) specifications despite them producing the same exact score for the original hausdorff dimension. This weakness measure can relate two different GR(1) - specifications without requiring a direct implication. Since the hausdorff dimension supports direct implication, their new weakness measure also still supports the original definition via direct implication, so it is a strict extension and improvement.

A more refined weakness Measure In a follow-up [CAG21], Cavezza et al. present a more refined version of their weakness measure. Here, instead of the tuple $(w_1 = \dim(\phi), w_2 = \dim(\phi^c))$, they create a triple $(w_0 = H(\phi), w_1 = \dim(\phi), w_2 = \dim(\phi^c))$ by prepending the entropy of the specification. This makes distinction easier, as entropy is faster to compute than hausdorff dimension. Cavezza et al. show, that in some cases entropy suffices and can be used to distinguish and rank different graphs in regards to weakness. Only in cases, where

entropy does not suffice, the more accurate weakness via hausdorff dimension and hausdorff complement is necessary and should be considered.

This new weakness measure, presented by Cavezza et al., aids us in creating a meaningful definition of restrictiveness, which we implement and investigate in this thesis. What is of great interest to us are the questions "How often do we need to rely on the hausdorff dimension and the hausdorff complement in our SML use case?" and "How often is the entropy measure sufficient?". For ideas on how to investigate this refer to Section 6.3.

3.2 Current approaches towards helping requirements engineers

The evolutionary algorithm by Schmelter et al., which we extended in this thesis, utilizes multi-objective evolution and generates new assumptions to make a given (presumed incomplete) SML specification realizable. During our thesis, we also came upon different strategies to support requirements engineers during the definition process. We present three approaches that either target a different goal (ensuring not realizability but well-separated-ness instead) or follow a different strategy (changing or even deleting existing assumptions and guarantees instead of creating new assumptions) or method (utilizing a completely different way to create assumptions).

3.2.1 "On well-separation of GR(1) specifications"

In their paper [MR16], Maoz and Ringert analyze a different quality of GR(1) specifications - the criterion of *well-separation*. Defined in 2011 by Klein and Pnueli [KP11], a specification is determined to be *well-separated* if the environment can not be forced into a violating state. A violating state in this case means a state of which there exists no path back to a state where the system has to make a decision / move. In a sense, this is the environment counterpart to the systems problem of realizability. Since SML is a variant of GR(1) specifications, the findings of Maoz and Ringert regarding general GR(1) specifications are of interest to us and SML specifications as well. In their work the authors show different kinds of specifications with different levels of severity of well-separated-ness, depending on how the environment is forced to violate its assumptions. They show how to identify a fairly small subset of environment assumptions that are already non-well-separated to narrow down the search space for the faulty part of the specification. Apart from fixing the environment part of the specification, they also propose that it might be sufficient to introduce *safety guarantees* for the system. With these, the System under Test (SUT) is no longer able to force the environment to violate its assumptions. This weaker form of well-separated-ness (well-separated-ness with respect to guarantees) might suffice for certain use cases. We believe that inspecting well-separation as a possible extension for the evolutionary algorithm can improve the generated solutions. We discuss how to possibly incorporate well-separated-ness into the evolutionary algorithm in Section 6.1

3.2.2 "Symbolic Repairs for GR(1) Specifications"

With their paper [MRS19] Maoz and Ringert provide insight into different methods to generate new assumptions. Firstly they explain, that unrealizability has to be caused by some action of the environment. A system can only then be unrealizable if the environment can force it to violate one of its guarantees. The authors call the way in which the environment does this a Counter Strategy (CS). They then propose two ways of generating new assumptions to make an SML specification realizable.

- *JVTS*: An approach that utilizes the perspective of the environment. They compute a symbolic CS for the environment and then generate new assumptions that target exactly

this CS and prevent the environment from executing it. In contrast to existing approaches utilizing existing CSs, the JVTs approach computes a symbolic representation of the CS, where other approaches had to compute the extensive concrete and state-based CS.

- *GLASS*: An approach that utilizes the perspective of the system. It computes new assumptions for the guarantees of the system, which ensure, that each guarantee can not be violated.

These two approaches both have their respective merits and drawbacks. The authors show, that in some cases the JVTs approach is incomplete and not able to compute a solution despite its existence. They also show the completeness of the GLASS approach, meaning that the GLASS approach always finds a valid solution by generating new assumptions to make the specification realizable, if such a solution exists. However, the GLASS approach is deterministic and can find only one specific solution, even if there are possibly multiple, maybe better, solutions existing. In summary, JVTs and GLASS could both serve as a good, albeit not perfect solution, when trying to repair an existing incomplete SML specification.

3.2.3 Automated Repair of Unrealisable LTL Specifications Guided by Model Counting

With their paper [BDC⁺21] Brizzio et al. take a completely different approach. Instead of focusing on just the assumptions (as Maoz and Ringert did mainly when researching how to combat non-well-separated-ness, or as Schmelter et al. and subsequently we are doing by evolving new assumptions to ensure realizability) the authors of this paper investigate the assumptions and guarantees that are already contained in the specification. This time the goal is aligned with ours - adjust an unrealizable specification to make it realizable. Where additional assumptions (as they are created by the evolutionary algorithm by Schmelter et al.) might suppress the environment, in that it can no longer enforce the exact event chain, that would lead to a violation of a systems guarantees, simply removing or adjusting the existing assumptions and guarantee might be a more efficient option. Brizzio et al. show in their paper that their approach can always find a realizable solution in regards to the 26 case studies they used for their evaluation. They use a heuristic search to augment or even delete some of the existing assumptions and guarantees while keeping a close look at the "similarity" of their new solution to the original specification. This is done to prevent the search algorithm from just putting out any realizable solution (e.g. an empty one).

3.2 CURRENT APPROACHES TOWARDS HELPING REQUIREMENTS ENGINEERS

We provide an extensive expose of different approaches that can all be used as a global definition of restrictiveness. This repository of different metrics enables us to compare and pitch the different approaches against each other. In Chapter 5 we observe how each of these definitions when implemented, affects the generated set of solutions, which the evolutionary algorithm puts out.

We start this chapter by presenting the current approach, implemented by Schmelter et al.. As demonstrated in the introductory example (see Section 1.3), this metric has its weaknesses, as it is not always able to distinguish between solutions of hugely different restrictiveness. In Section 4.2 we first present some preliminary metrics for restrictiveness for state machines in general, that are based on measures that have already been defined. We explain how these can be adapted to SML as well. In Section 4.3 we present adjustments that can be made to the state graph itself to capture the restrictiveness imposed on the environment, instead of the general restrictiveness of the entire state graph.

After that, we present how we combined the general graph restrictiveness metrics and the adjustments to fit the environment restrictiveness (see Section 4.4) to create the different *candidates* that we analyzed in our evaluation.

Apart from the theoretical work on restrictiveness, we also present our means to utilize this restrictiveness in the context of the evolutionary generation of new solutions. For this, we present our extension to the MOEAFramework in Section 4.5, which enabled us to easily specify every metric as a minimization objective, without being restricted to evaluating it as a value of type "double".

4.1 Current Approach

A first and very simple approach was already implemented in the evolutionary generation algorithm by Schmelter et al.. It evaluates a penalty for a generated solution based on the restrictiveness of individual messages. This approach was shown to not sufficiently describe restrictiveness in the example during the problem description (see Section 1.3). Nonetheless, we want to incorporate it into our study, as a base to compare our other definitions with. We refer to this metric as R1 (Restrictiveness Metric 1).

4.2 General Restrictiveness of Graphs

A good approach for restrictiveness can be obtained by measuring the state graph resulting from an SML specification (see Section 2.6.2). Additional freedom (less restrictiveness) for the environment would become visible in additional paths/choices for environment-controlled states. However, we need to keep in mind, that the graph itself contains the complexity of not only the environment but the SUT as well. Nonetheless, these metrics, constructed from the state graph itself, can serve as meaningful indicators for our target.

4.2.1 Size of the resulting State Graph

As a quite simple approach, that is perhaps more accurate than the original R1, we measure the size of the state graph, that is created from the generated specification. For this we have two different options.

- *node count*: Defining size by the number of possible states. A high value here means, that we removed as little as possible from (or added as much as possible to) the original state space with our new assumptions. A problem arises when thinking of fringe cases for possible state graphs. For example, a state graph that represents a long chain (o-o-o-o-o....) would have a very high node count. The decisive freedom of the environment, however, is pretty low in such a case. We deduce, that there are at least edge cases, in which the node count is not sufficient.
- *edge count*: Defining size by the number of possible edges. We think that this approach might be at least as, and maybe even more accurate than the former definition. The edge count metric seems to be able to handle the aforementioned fringe cases better. A smaller state graph with higher connectivity (more edges) would be regarded as less restrictive, than a big (many nodes) state graph with lower connectivity (fewer edges). However, if the graph is sufficiently big, it may be preferred over a much smaller fully connected graph, simply due to its size (e.g. fully connected Graph of size 4 (6 edges) vs. a chain of length 7). Nonetheless, this definition may suffice for our use case (shrinking an existing state graph), as such fringe cases seem to be far off the norm. As with the node count, a high edge count value means, that we removed as little as possible from (or added as much as possible to) the original state space with our new assumptions.

Either way, we then define the restrictiveness of a solution by the negative of the size of its resulting state space to obtain a value that can be minimized (as is required for applying the MOEA framework). These approaches will from now on be referred to as R2 (node count) and R3 (edge count).

4.2.2 Decisive Power of the State Graph

As another approach, we define restrictiveness by measuring not just the size, but also the number of possible decisions available in the resulting state space of a solution. Formally we define the *decision count* in a graph G as $\sum_{v \in V(G)} (|outgoingEdges(v)| - 1)$. This definition should in theory be even better in measuring connectivity than the edge count since it only adds to the value when there are at least two edges / two different paths going out from any node. This prevents the metric from preferring big, less connected graphs over smaller more connected ones, which could in theory happen with node and edge count. Again, a high value represents the many choices one can make while traversing the graph. We then again define restrictiveness as the negative of this decision count value to obtain a minimization objective for the MOEA framework. We call this decision-based approach R4.

4.2.3 Entropy Measure of the State Graph

In their paper [WCT⁺19], Wan et al. present a variant of the entropy measure, which is supposed to encapsulate the complexity of a graph by determining its growth rate of acyclic subgraphs. In the context of state spaces for SML specifications, this means the growth rate of distinct paths to take, before returning to an already visited state. We apply this measure to the state graph created from the SML specification, to serve as another candidate for calculating a restrictiveness value for generated solutions from the evolutionary generation. Here, more distinct acyclic paths indicate more choices (and thus less restrictiveness). Given that, we propose that the negative entropy value for the graph can be treated as a restrictiveness objective for the evolutionary algorithm. This metric is from now on being referred to as R5.

4.2.4 Finite Hausdorff dimension of the State Graph

In his papers, [Alo16] and [Alo15], Juan M. Alonso presents a measure called "finite hausdorff dimension", which is supposed to measure the complexity of a graph. We apply this to the state graph G created from the SML specification. Here, the different possibilities for transitioning to new states represent distinct possible choices. In our case, we have an even simpler case, as we are working with state spaces corresponding to unweighted graphs (the distance of states is determined by hops), as each state will be reached by a simple message / event from its predecessor. With the help of this definition, we design a candidate for the restrictiveness of a generated specification as $\frac{1}{dim_f(G)}$, where G is the state graph, that corresponds to the specification. Here a high value resembles a high amount of choices, and thus low restrictiveness of the newly generated specification. A probable problem that we can anticipate at this point is, that computing the finite dimension of the graph is NP-complete, which requires us to run sufficient performance tests, to figure out if this poses a negative impact on the evolutionary generation algorithm. We evaluated computational overhead in Section 5.4.1. As before, to obtain a minimization objective for our Multi-objective evolutionary algorithm, we take the negative value of the hausdorff dimension as our objective value. This negative of the finite hausdorff dimension of the state graph is our metric candidate R6.

4.2.5 Inverse Weakness Measure

To define a metric for the overall complexity of the resulting specification, we want to utilize the weakness measure proposed by Cavezza et al. (see Section 3.1). In their paper, they propose a weakness relation, that is applicable over general GR(1) Specifications [BJP⁺12]. This should be applicable on SML as well, as SML serves as a natural extension of GR(1) Specifications for guarantee/assumption scenarios. This approach is the most complex, but also very likely to be the most accurate definition of restrictiveness that we have currently found. As presented in Section 3.1, there are two possible ways to define weakness, we decided on the latter one. The 2021 definition of weakness specifies entropy as a preliminary decision before utilizing the hausdorff dimension to differentiate between solutions. Both of the original definitions rely on the complement of a given SML specification as a tiebreaker for solutions that are evaluated equally using entropy or the hausdorff dimension. However, implementing the hausdorff complement of SML specifications requires a lot more research, so we settled on implementing a simpler version of these metrics, ignoring the hausdorff complement. We define metric candidate R7 as the simple weakness measure, consisting only of entropy and the hausdorff dimension. For future work, it might be interesting to investigate whether R8 (the regular weakness measure) can improve the evolutionary generation (see Section 6.2) To obtain a minimization objective, we extended the MOEAFramework (see Section 4.5) to be able to specify single objectives containing

multiple values. This objective consists of the negative entropy value and the negative hausdorff dimension value of the state graph for the given specification. With this, we have an objective, which we are able to minimize for the MOEAframework.

4.3 Environment Restrictiveness in SML State Graphs

All of the aforementioned examples could work on the original state space created from an SML-Specification. Apart from just implementing them as is, we wanted to find additional optimization techniques for our domain. To this extent, we present some ideas for adjustment of the state space or design additional new objectives to be used together with our new restrictiveness objective.

4.3.1 Cleaning up Super Steps (S)

Within our generated state space there are cases where the system has to react in a certain way and can only perform an exact sequence of transitions (A \rightarrow B \rightarrow C). Collecting these steps and performing just a single step instead of multiple ones might affect the metric candidates for general state graphs. To enable these super-steps we gather neighboring states and merge them, where the only transitions possible are via system actions.

Figure 4.1: Super Steps - possible contractions

This image shows an example of a graph and how our super steps can be used to contract it. The nodes resemble vertices in the given graph, and the edges show how the vertices are connected. The labels on the nodes are just identifiers. Each edge is either labeled "Environment" or "System", to indicate whether the message that is sent to switch states originates from an environmental actor or the SUT. Thick nodes resemble final nodes, of which there are no further outgoing edges. Nodes and edges are colored in green if the super step adjustment removes them from the graph.

As shown in Figure 4.1, our super step adjustment can augment a state graph to enable our metrics to focus on the complexity / restrictiveness of the environment rather than both,

environment and SUT. Nodes can only be removed if they interact with just the system, not the environment (see In State 1). They can also only be removed if they are part of only one edge (in any direction). We differentiate between two possible kinds of states (and associated edges) that can be removed for our adjustment.

- *Single Outgoing*: A node can be removed, if its set of outgoing edges is of size one, and all of its outgoing edges are "System"-edges. In the graphic above, these are the nodes "InState 2" and "InState 3".
- *Single Incoming*: A node can be removed, if its set of incoming edges is of size one, and all of its incoming edges are "System"-edges. In the graphic above, these are the nodes "OutState 2" and "OutState 3".

In any case, the node and its corresponding edge, which made it possible for the node to be removed, are deleted, and the remaining edges are transferred to its neighbors to maintain the logic of the remaining graph.

4.3.2 Adjusting the Candidates (C)

Since we are not actually interested in the complexity / restrictiveness of the entire graph, but just the environment portion of it, we propose additional adjustments for some of the restrictiveness metrics.

State Graph Size Regarding the size of the state space one can easily distinguish between nodes/edges that belong to the system or that belong to the environment. To address this issue, we adjusted the metric candidates to filter for only environment-controlled states / edges for the respective restrictiveness metric.

Decisive Power As for the state graph size, we can also filter the edges used for calculating the number of decisions of the environment.

Entropy, Hausdorff Dimension and Weakness Measure Due to the complexity of the given metrics, adjustments for SML are not as easy. However, we believe that the super step adjustment serves well for that exact purpose. As we will see in Section 5.4.2, we were able to show, that the super step adjustment had the same effect on the previous metrics, as the individual adjustment.

4.3.3 Dealing with Environment Violations (EV)

As presented in Section 3.2.1, environment violations occur, when the SML specification contains ways for the system to force the environment to violate its guarantees. In some sense, these violations are even more restrictive than any graph measure one can think of. We propose two ways of how to deal with these violations and how to incorporate them into the evolutionary algorithm.

Removing Environment Violations (EV_1) Similar to the super steps approach (see Section 4.3.1), one could think of adjusting the state graph, to make the proposed metric candidates more efficient. The ability to reach a state, where the environment has already violated one of its guarantees, should be regarded as even more restrictive, than not being able to reach it. However, current metric candidates might add a positive value to the graph for containing additional nodes / edges or decisions despite them leading to an environment violation. We propose,

that adjusting the state space by removing the nodes and paths that have to lead to such a "dead end" could improve the restrictiveness metrics.

Penalizing Environment Violations (EV_2) Going a step further, one could also incorporate a penalty for such environment violations. They indicate states in which the environment has no distinct choices at all. Whatever actions it may perform, it can not leave the violating state. Following that, we can determine, that the mere existence of these violations can be interpreted as more restrictive. This penalty can be incorporated in the evolution of least restrictive solutions in multiple ways. One possible way would be to add the penalty value to the Restrictiveness Objective as a secondary value and figure out some new comparator for this new kind of objective. The much simpler way to incorporate this penalty into the generation would be to specify an individual objective for it. This way, MOEAFramework naturally evolves solutions that tend to contain fewer environment violations.

4.4 Proposed Metric Candidates

To investigate if and how any of the general graph restrictiveness metrics and SML environment adjustments affect the ranking of generated solutions, one could construct a matrix containing $1(\text{the original R1}) + 7(\text{graph metric candidates}) * (2^3)(\text{environment adjustments to be enabled}) = 48$ distinct restrictiveness metric candidates.

Due to our limited time, we were able to only investigate and evaluate

$1(\text{the original R1}) + 6(\text{graph metric candidates}) * 2^1(\text{environment adjustments enabled}) = 13$ candidates.

We present these in Table 4.1

Identifier	Restrictiveness Metric	Environment Adjustments		
		S	C	EV
$R1$	Local Penalty (Schmelter et al.)	0	0	0
$R2$	State Graph Size (Node Count)	0	✓	0
$R2_S$	State Graph Size (Node Count)	✓	✓	0
$R3$	State Graph Size (Edge Count)	0	✓	0
$R3_S$	State Graph Size (Edge Count)	✓	✓	0
$R4$	Number of Decisions	0	✓	0
$R4_S$	Number of Decisions	✓	✓	0
$R5$	Entropy (Wan et al.)	0	0	0
$R5_S$	Entropy (Wan et al.)	✓	0	0
$R6$	Finite Hausdorff Dimension (Alonso)	0	0	0
$R6_S$	Finite Hausdorff Dimension (Alonso)	✓	0	0
$R7$	Weakness (Cavezza et al.)	0	0	0
$R7_S$	Weakness (Cavezza et al.)	✓	0	0

Table 4.1: Candidates for our restrictiveness metrics

From now on, when we refer to metric candidates we will use the identifier as presented in Table 4.1. Each metric is identified by its original general graph metric and an optional extension determining which of the adjustments is currently active. (e.g. The Weakness Measure by Cavezza et al. with merged super steps is identified as $R7_S$.)

To find out how exactly all of these definitions behave, we implemented each of them and analyzed the resulting generated solutions for the given specifications in Chapter 5

4.5 Extending the MOEAFramework for general Objectives

While defining a new metric for restrictiveness by itself is the most important part of the research, it is not sufficient for solving the problem just in theory. We also have to integrate the new restrictiveness objective into the evolutionary algorithm. We utilize the current algorithm, which uses the MOEAFramework (see Section 2.8 and specify the restrictiveness metric as a minimization objective. Originally the MOEAFramework was only able to support objectives of type "double", as those can easily be minimized. Since our metrics can in some cases consist of different data types (e. g. weakness by Cavezza et al. is a tuple of doubles), we needed to set up an extension, that is capable of supporting all of our metrics. For this purpose, we created the *MOEAFrameworkGeneralExtension*. This extension enables users to set up *Objectives* with individual comparators. Using this extension, we were able to utilize the MOEAFramework with general objectives and have the evolutionary algorithm optimize for all of our new restrictiveness metrics.

To make an educated recommendation and determine if any of the metric candidates we came up with can serve as a good extension for the evolutionary generation of environment assumptions, we need to analyze each candidate in depth. To this extent, we present the following evaluation setup.

5.1 Setting

For the original evolutionary algorithm by Schmelter et al., there exists a public codebase¹, which can be arbitrarily extended for additional optimization goals and metrics. For our evaluation we augmented the projects and set up a standalone maven build, that is now executed via a gitlab pipeline². We also have access to the special version of the MOEAFramework Schmelter et al. used for their generation³, and their version of the scenariotools repository⁴, which we both forked and adjusted for standalone execution / build as well⁵ ⁶. Using this code base, we implemented and compared different variations of the restrictiveness metrics defined in Section 4.4 to be used as minimization objectives. This allowed us to apply the different metrics on single evolution search runs, enabling us to directly compare the results. Using this, we then applied the evolutionary search on the existing SML-research-examples "Production Cell" and "EBEAS" and gathered exemplary data for each of the metrics.

All of the code resources used for this project are stored and archived on a gitlab server of the University of Paderborn (upb). Since safe storage may not be guaranteed via this gitlab server, we also provide a final version of this project via zenodo⁷.

5.2 Experiment

To evaluate the different approaches towards defining restrictiveness, we conducted a case study as defined by Kitchenham[KBP11]. For our example cases, which serve as a base to gather

¹<https://git.cs.uni-paderborn.de/david.schmelter/de.fraunhofer.iem.swt.geneticsscenarios/-/tree/features/evaluation>

²<https://git.cs.uni-paderborn.de/nikob/de.fraunhofer.iem.swt.geneticsscenarios/-/pipelines>

³<https://git.cs.uni-paderborn.de/david.schmelter/MOEAFramework>

⁴<https://git.cs.uni-paderborn.de/david.schmelter/scenariotools-sml>

⁵<https://git.cs.uni-paderborn.de/nikob/scenariotools-sml/-/pipelines>

⁶<https://git.cs.uni-paderborn.de/nikob/MOEAFramework/-/pipelines>

⁷<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5520618>

experiment results, we chose the SML-research-examples "Production Cell" (which we also used in the introduction Section 1.1) and "EBEAS", for which the code resources are available in the appendix (see Appendix A.1 and Appendix A.2). With the help of these examples and a sufficient amount of distinct test runs we were able to gather statistically significant data (see Section 5.4) supporting us in our recommendation.

Research Questions To analyze the different candidates we formulate the following questions to answer with the help of our case study.

1. Does any of the metric candidates for restrictiveness impose an overhead significant enough to affect the runtime or success of the evolutionary algorithm?
2. How do the different restrictiveness candidates correlate?
3. What quality do solutions have, when evolved using any of the metric candidates as an objective.

Goal We use these research questions to enhance our understanding of the different metrics for restrictiveness, so that we can prepare for answering the one truly important question: *Which of the metric candidates do we recommend for further research / use?*

5.2.1 Strategy

To answer the questions presented in Section 5.2 we employ different strategies for each of them. In all cases, we evaluate our different metric candidates, as defined in Section 4.4 - sometimes comparing them to others. During any run of the evolutionary algorithm, we gathered the computed values for each metric candidate, as well as the time it took to compute it. We exported these values into a database to now analyze and explain.

Does any of the Metrics impose an Overhead significant enough to affect the Runtime of the Evolutionary Algorithm? For the first question of computational overhead, we introduced a simple clock measuring the time each computation of the restrictiveness metric takes. With this, we can compare the computation time of different metric candidates and determine how much more effort is required to calculate them. With this, we are also able to compare the overall time the evolutionary algorithm took to compute the final solution candidates to any single metric candidate's computational time. This enables us to find the proportional computing time any of the restrictiveness candidates adds to the complete generation process.

How do the different restrictiveness candidates correlate? For finding correlations between different restrictiveness candidates we rely on the so-called *Kendall's τ* which we summarized in Section 2.9.1.

We implemented Kendall's τ for comparing and finding correlations between different restrictiveness metrics by simply reading from the database table, which is set up during any run of the evolutionary algorithm. As explained before, to this extent, any single evolution run always has to compute values for each restrictiveness metric. Due to the inherent randomness of our candidates and the generated solutions, we require a sufficiently large number of generated solutions to be able to make qualified statements on the correlation of the different metric candidates. In Section 5.5.2 we explain in detail how statistically significant our findings are.

What quality do solutions have, when evolved using any of the metric candidates as an objective When trying to understand the quality of certain metrics in regards to the evolved solutions, when applied as an objective for the optimization, one has to understand that there exists no absolute metric for "good", which could be analyzed. This is a hindrance. To be able to make a recommendation for a certain metric, we want to take into account the effect of applying this metric as an objective has on the evolved solutions. To this extent we make use of our examples "ProductionCell" and "EBEAS" and perform multiple evolutionary runs, to see if we can find / observe certain reproducible patterns / properties in the evolved scenarios. For the qualitative evaluation we have two goals:

1. Ensure that the new objective does not pose a *threat* to the quality. This could manifest in e.g. the generated solutions not being consistent / feasible / realizable anymore. This can be done automatically, by simply ensuring that the number of *consistent* (realizable) solutions generated by the algorithm is not affected, or checking if the algorithm is still able to produce a viable pareto front.
2. Find and evaluate a positive impact on the evolved solutions. To give an example, a metric could force the generated solutions to preserve as many capabilities of the environment as possible. This could manifest in a generated solution candidate being part of the pareto front and replacing another one, where the restrictiveness for the environment would be much higher. In particular, we would want the evolved solutions to have lower restrictiveness (according to whatever restrictiveness metric was used as an objective). To give an example; if we used the restrictiveness metric based on entropy as our objective we would want the evolved solutions, that are finally presented to the requirements engineer, to have as high an entropy value as possible.

5.3 Threats to validity

We are aware of possible problems and threats, that could negatively impact our evaluation and, in the worst case, affect our test data and lead to wrong evaluation results. With this section, we want to address those problems and challenges and argue why our data has in fact not fallen prey to those threats.

5.3.1 Mistakes during development

We are aware that software is prone to error. Especially since our research deals with incomplete / erroneous code as well, albeit at the level of SML - specifications in contrast to classical java/kotlin/python code as used in this project. To ensure that our code is as resilient as possible and works as expected, we created some unit tests for individual components, which we felt deserved some extra attention (graph manipulation, restrictiveness metrics, data types, comparators).

5.3.2 The measurement of Quality

In our strategy, we introduced our goal of a "qualitative" evaluation of the metric candidates. While there currently exists no comparable "good" metric for us to compare our metrics to, we still believe that we can make an argument for the quality of our solutions. First and foremost we want to ensure that our restrictiveness metric does not have a negative influence on the evolved solutions. For this, we investigated whether the evolutionary generation was still able to produce realizable / consistent solutions. We also want to ensure that our restrictiveness metric has the desired effect of reducing the environment restrictiveness of the created solutions. To this

extend we plotted the behavior of the evolutionary algorithm in regards to each restrictiveness metrics over the different iterations and compared that to the original metric $R1$ (Section 4.1).

5.3.3 Statistical Significance

Our evaluation is based on a small case study. Additionally, the evolutionary generation of assumptions possesses inherent randomness, which makes it difficult to simply make factual claims, since we cannot produce deterministic outcomes. Given that, we need to argue why our results can be translated to general application. This is to be done for each statement / claim independently since we are working with different data sets each time. As such we will argue for statistical significance for each claim that we make (see Section 5.5.2).

5.3.4 Time Measurement in multi-threading ?

Originally the algorithm by Schmelter et al. evaluates individual solution candidates in parallel on different threads using multiple cores. This could affect our evaluation of time spent during the calculation of each restrictiveness metric and especially affects the proportional time of the overall run for each restrictiveness candidate. However, we compare the runtime of a specific metric (which is done in parallel for different candidates) to the full runtime of the evaluation of that exact candidate. This means that we only ever compare runtimes of actions that were performed in the same threads. One could argue that this parallelization would maybe cause different threads to stop and wait for other processes to finish, which could then affect our measurement again. However, we believe that this inference averages out on a global scale, as we investigated the runtimes of over 780.000 evolved candidates.

5.4 Results / Data

To figure out how our restrictiveness metrics behave, we gathered exemplary scores for each distinct metric over the same generated solutions. Below we present the different results we were able to gather from implementing Section 5.2.1. For the runs that produced the data we analyzed, we ran the evolutionary algorithm on 30 seeds for 2.000 evolved candidates per seed. We set up an evaluation run for each of the specified 13 metric candidates (see Section 4.4) and generated a grand total of $30 * 2.000 * 13 = 780.000$ possible candidate solutions. This experiment was repeated once for every case study example ("Production Cell"⁸ and "EBEAS"⁹). We make use of the resulting data for analyzing the different candidates for restrictiveness metrics and environment adjustments.

5.4.1 Computational Overhead

Table 5.1 and Table 5.2 show the individual computational overhead of calculating each and every implemented metric candidate. In these tables you can observe the maximum and absolute computational time (in milliseconds) it took to evaluate a certain candidate metric during an extensive search. The proportion of the complete evaluation computation time is calculated on average by dividing a metrics overall execution time by the complete evaluation overall execution time * 100%. Note, that the table for the EBEAS example is missing the lines for $R5$ and $R5_s$. This is due to the fact that this metric was not applicable with the more complex example, as it was causing runtime errors. We explain and evaluate this in detail in Section 5.5.1.

⁸Appendix A.1

⁹Appendix A.2

Table 5.1: Computational Overhead - Production Cell

Metric Identifier	max. computing time (in milliseconds)	absolute computing time (in milliseconds)	proportion of complete evaluation computing time
complete evaluation	183204	15803155	100.0%
<i>completeevaluation</i>	320,508	158,217,985	100%
<i>R1</i>	128	9,116	0.0058%
<i>R2</i>	224	220,797	0.1396%
<i>R2_S</i>	278	934,798	0.5909%
<i>R3</i>	268	170,634	0.1079%
<i>R3_S</i>	296	769,004	0.4861%
<i>R4</i>	300	196,861	0.1245%
<i>R4_S</i>	381	765,399	0.4838%
<i>R5</i>	263,653	6,106,941	3.8599%
<i>R5_S</i>	55,027	1,866,232	1.1796%
<i>R6</i>	4,300	33,017,680	20.8685%
<i>R6_S</i>	526	3,077,810	1.9453%
<i>R7</i>	4,617	33,461,738	21.1492%
<i>R7_S</i>	442	4,143,560	2.6189%

Table 5.2: Computational Overhead - EBEAS

Metric Identifier	max. computing time	absolute computing time	proportion of computing time
<i>completeevaluation</i>	24,573	134,736,109	100%
<i>R1</i>	60	6,397	0.0048%
<i>R2</i>	41	127,666	0.0948%
<i>R2_S</i>	74	381,279	0.283%
<i>R3</i>	43	107,921	0.0801%
<i>R3_S</i>	55	305,970	0.2271%
<i>R4</i>	45	120,993	0.0898%
<i>R4_S</i>	58	300,943	0.2234%
<i>R6</i>	10,704	18,191,576	13.5017%
<i>R6_S</i>	920	2,054,162	1.5246%
<i>R7</i>	11,133	22,615,312	16.7849%
<i>R7_S</i>	990	2,761,554	2.0497%

What's interesting here, is that the super step adjustment increases the computing time for the simple metrics (R2, R3, R4) by a factor of 3 to 6, while it significantly decreases / improves the computing time for the more complex metrics, that analyze / traverse the graph in depth. This showcases the importance of the super steps for not only finding better solutions in regards to environment restrictiveness but also finding them much faster. Looking at the impact, that each metric has on the overall computing time, one can safely say that the simple metrics (R1 to R4) do not impose a significant delay on the search with a proportional runtime of less than 1%. R5 requires a little more effort for computation with up to 10% of the overall candidate evaluation. The metrics R6 and R7 stand out, as they can take up roughly 20% of the complete evaluation time each. This is worse than it seems since the combined 50% of all the

calculated metrics are already part of the complete evaluation time. If one were to implement the searches on their own without actually calculating all other metrics as well, this would amount to an actual increase in runtime of $\frac{20\%}{50\%} = 40\%$ compared to not calculating any metric at all. Thankfully, we can see that the super step versions of these expensive metrics perform significantly better. These versions reduce the computational overhead to the level of less than 3% of the complete evaluation time per metric. This amounts to a computational overhead of $\frac{3\%}{50\%} = < 10\%$.

5.4.2 Correlation of Metrics

For finding correlations between different metrics we made use of the *Kendall τ coefficient* as explained in Section 5.2.1. We compared the different preferences of the metrics when pitching two of the possible evolved solutions against each other. For this comparison, we selected 20,000 random entries out of the 780,000 created solution candidates for each of our SML examples. This allows for $\binom{20,000}{2} = 20,000 * 19,999 / 2 = 199,990,000$ or roughly 200 million preference decisions per example.

In the following tables, *R1* to *R6* are just the regular metric identifiers. Since *R7* consists of a combination of the entropy value and the hausdorff dimension, we view these values separately. Here *R7_E* is the entropy part of the simplified weakness measure and *R7_H* is the hausdorff dimension part of the simplified weakness measure (see Section 4.2.5).

For presentation purposes, we split the full correlation table into the direct comparison between different metrics and the comparison of individual metrics to their super step version. For the full correlation table refer to Appendix C.3.

As in Table 5.2, the "EBEAS" example does not contain information about the metric *R5*, as this metric was not applicable to this example (see Section 5.5.1).

Table 5.3: Correlation of Metric Candidates - Production Cell

	<i>R1</i>	<i>R2</i>	<i>R3</i>	<i>R4</i>	<i>R5</i>	<i>R6</i>	<i>R7_E</i>	<i>R7_H</i>
<i>R1</i>	1	0.0799	0.0899	0.0879	0.1036	0.1436	-0.057	0.1512
<i>R2</i>	0.0782	1	0.9378	0.8639	0.6558	0.6987	0.3291	0.6975
<i>R3</i>	0.0865	0.9374	1	0.9163	0.6632	0.7322	0.3501	0.7315
<i>R4</i>	0.0953	0.8652	0.9161	1	0.642	0.7427	0.3767	0.7361
<i>R5</i>	0.1005	0.6539	0.6655	0.6415	1	0.6316	0.279	0.628
<i>R6</i>	0.1467	0.6961	0.7299	0.7388	0.631	1	0.3924	1
<i>R7_E</i>	-0.0597	0.3173	0.3456	0.3716	0.2737	0.3891	1	0.3959
<i>R7_H</i>	0.1491	0.6954	0.7314	0.739	0.6299	1	0.3959	1

Table 5.4: Correlation of Metric Candidates - EBEAS

	<i>R1</i>	<i>R2</i>	<i>R3</i>	<i>R4</i>	<i>R5</i>	<i>R6</i>	<i>R7_E</i>	<i>R7_H</i>
<i>R1</i>	1	0.0321	0.0641	0.0644	-	0.1778	0.1034	0.1647
<i>R2</i>	0.0271	1	0.8814	0.8185	-	0.5595	0.5236	0.5593
<i>R3</i>	0.0595	0.8832	1	0.9253	-	0.6214	0.543	0.6235
<i>R4</i>	0.0699	0.8179	0.9249	1	-	0.6293	0.5432	0.6327
<i>R5</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>R6</i>	0.1699	0.5606	0.6272	0.6318	-	1	0.6409	1
<i>R7_E</i>	0.1104	0.5212	0.5458	0.5421	-	0.6445	1	0.6382
<i>R7_H</i>	0.1756	0.5653	0.6229	0.6324	-	1	0.6406	1

Table 5.3 and Table 5.4 show information about the direct correlation coefficient of different metrics. What we can observe here is that the simple metrics $R2$ and $R3$ are very closely related (coefficient > 0.8). We can also see, that $R1$ seems to be independent from all of the other metrics, since its Kendall τ coefficient is very close to 0, in the range of $[-0.16, 0.07]$. Metric $R4$ seems to be more closely related to $R2$ and $R3$ (coefficients of roughly > 0.5) than to $R5$ and $R6$ (coefficients of < 0.4), which themselves are largely independent from one another as well (coefficient of < 0.4).

Table 5.5: Correlation of Environment Adjustments

Production Cell		EBEAS	
Metric Identifier	Kendall τ Correlation to it's super step version	Metric Identifier	Kendall τ Correlation to it's super step version
$R2$	1.0	$R2$	1.0
$R3$	1.0	$R3$	1.0
$R4$	1.0	$R4$	1.0
$R5$	0.9282	$R5$	-
$R6$	0.7995	$R6$	0.671
$R7_E$	0.9581	$R7_E$	0.854
$R7_H$	0.7973	$R7_H$	0.6604

In Table 5.5 we show information about the correlation coefficient of metrics when applying the super step adjustment (see Section 4.3.1).

What we can observe in these tables is that the 3 simple metrics all are in perfect agreement with their super step adjusted counterparts for both of our examples. This is due to the fact, that we already adjusted those for gathering information about only the environment by filtering states / edges that are controlled by the SUT. What this proves, however, is that our super step adjustment does not affect the parts of the state graph, that are controlled by the environment, because with utmost certainty that would have affected at least one of the 200 million preference decisions.

We can also observe, that $R5$ and $R7_E$, the entropy part of the simplified weakness measure, almost perfectly correlate with their respective super step counterpart as well. However, we did not perform any adjustments to fit these entropy values to environment restrictiveness, rather than full restrictiveness of the entire state graph. We believe, that this is due to the fact that the system has a rather reactionary nature. It can not decide what to do as often as the environment, because in most cases the guarantees are stricter than the assumptions.

In all correlation tables, you can also see, that the values for $R7_H$ and $R6$ are the same and that there is a perfect correlation between these two metrics. In the case of $R5$ and $R7_E$ this is not the case, despite both metrics measure some notion of entropy. This is because, we reused the hausdorff dimension as calculated for $R6$ as the hausdorff dimension part in $R7_H$. In contrast to that, the entropy value of $R5$ is evaluated by counting distinct acyclic paths in the graph, and the entropy value of $R7_E$ is calculated via the eigenvalue of its distance matrix.

5.4.3 Quality of Metrics

To analyze the quality of our restrictiveness metrics, we implemented multiple metrics as defined in Section 5.2.1. To find out how a single metric would affect the evolutionary algorithm, we ran multiple search runs, with a different metric utilized as a minimization objective each time. For this, we measured the metric value of the generated candidate populations over the iterations

of the respective search run. The set of candidates was filtered to just include the candidates that were part of the final pareto front in each run, that would possibly be presented to the requirements engineer. There are different graphs for the distinct runs in which a different metric was used as a minimization objective. The "OBJECTIVEID"s from 1 to 7 map directly to the respective restrictiveness metric R_i . The "OBJECTIVEID"s from 8 to 13 map directly to the restrictiveness metrics $R(i\%6)_S$ (e.g OBJECTIVEID = 11 \rightarrow $R5_S$).

We show here the most interesting results that we were able to gather from that measurement. An exhaustive list of all our measurements is given in the abstract (see Appendix C)

Metric Behavior - Production Cell What we can observe in Figure 5.1 and Figure 5.2 is the average behavior of those metrics over evaluation runs on the "Production Cell" example, where we optimized for them. We can see, that specifying any metric as our minimization objective achieves better results for that specific metric than relying on the current/former implementation $R1$, which was used by Schmelter et al. up until now.

Furthermore, choosing one of our new metrics seems to change the behavior of the evolutionary search, in that even during later iterations, it still finds new pareto optimal solutions.

We also can observe, that the evolutionary generation (at least parameterized as it is currently) rarely ever finds new, potential improvements after iteration 100 when optimizing for metric $R2$, as there are just a few new pareto optimal candidates found after that.

Figure 5.1: Quality of $R4$ - Production Cell

This plot show the $R4$ values of the candidates that were generated in each iteration during the evolutionary algorithm. The light graph represents the candidates, that were generated during the runs in which the $R1$ objective was active. The dark graph shows the values that were achieved when the metric $R4$ was used as the minimization objective.

Metric Behavior - EBEAS What we can observe in Figure 5.3 and Figure 5.4 is the average behavior of metrics over evaluation runs on the "Production Cell" example, where we optimized for them in comparison to the behavior of their super step versions. We can see, that for the "EBEAS" example as well, specifying any metric as our minimization objective achieves better results for that specific metric compared to using the existing $R1$.

Additionally to validating our results from the "Production Cell" example (see Section 5.4.3), we can also see, that the super steps variant of either metric produces similar results to the ones from the metric without the super step adjustment.

Figure 5.2: Quality of R7 - Production Cell

Similar to Figure 5.1, this plot shows the $R7$ values of the pareto optimal candidates that were generated in each iteration during the evolutionary algorithm. Again, the light graph represents the values that were achieved when utilizing $R1$ as the objective and the dark graph shows the values that were achieved when the measured metric ($R7$) was used as the minimization objective.

Figure 5.3: Quality of $R4_S$ - EBEAS

This plot shows the $R4_S$ values of the candidates that were generated in each iteration during the evolutionary algorithm when applied to the "EBEAS" example. In addition to the graphs for the $R1$ and $R4_S$ runs, we also plotted the candidates of the run where we optimized for $R4$ (without the super step adjustment) to enable direct comparison of the behavior of the original metric to the behavior of its super step variant.

Direct Comparison of the most promising metrics Utilizing these performance results and the runtime results (Section 5.4.1) we preemptively decided on 3 metrics to recommend: $[R4, R6_S, R7_S]$. With the hope of finding a definitive optimal metric, we decided to compare the performance of those metrics directly. In Figure 5.5 and Figure 5.6 you can observe the direct comparison of the metrics $[R4, R6_S, R7_S]$. Like for the other plots showcasing the quality / performance of the metrics, these plots show the $R4$ values of the pareto optimal candidates that were generated in each iteration during the evolutionary algorithm. Again, there is one graph per metric, representing the values achieved when utilizing this metric as the objective. Sadly, all of these metrics seem to perform equally well for all of the metric values (see Appendix C.2 and there is no significant difference in the restrictiveness of the created candidates.

Figure 5.4: Quality of $R7_S$ - EBEAS

Similar to Figure 5.3, this plot shows the $R7_S$ values of the pareto optimal candidates that were generated in each iteration during the evolutionary algorithm. Again, the light graph represents the values, that were achieved when utilizing $R1$ as the objective, the dotted graph shows the values, that were achieved when utilizing the $R7$ metric without the super step adjustment and the dark graph shows the values that were achieved when the measured metric ($R7_S$) with the super step adjustment was used as the minimization objective.

Figure 5.5: Direct comparison - Production Cell

Figure 5.6: Direct comparison - EBEAS

5.5 Answering our Research Questions

With our test results at hand (see Section 5.4) we want to answer the research questions we proposed for our case study.

5.5.1 Do any of the metrics have a significant impact on the runtime / success of the evolutionary algorithm?

The different metrics have vastly different computation times, ranging from a few milliseconds to even multiple minutes for a single solution candidate. Despite that, none of them significantly increased the runtime of the evolutionary algorithm, with the most expensive one, being the simplified weakness measurement built from the weakness measure of Cavezza et al., adding an extra 80% to the runtime of the program when used as the sole restrictiveness metric. What's interesting though, is that even that can be significantly improved by just applying the super step adjustment first. Shrinking the graph down in size and thus decreasing the required computation time allows us to reduce the overhead of this metric to just 10%.

Concession During our evaluation, we found, that the $R5$ metric poses a great risk for the evolutionary algorithm. While in most cases, it runs smoothly and produces a result 3 times faster than $R6$ and $R7$, it can cause an "out of memory" - exception at runtime due to some sort of memory leak. Gathering all possible acyclic paths contained in an SML state graph is a very expensive operation, which, if not sufficiently provided, uses up the entire memory available. While the "Production Cell" example can run on roughly 4GB of RAM, in most cases, we were not able to have even a single successful execution on the "EBEAS" example when calculating the $R5$ or $R5_S$ metric. With that in mind, we do not recommend using $R5$ as an objective, or at least not using our implementation for it.

5.5.2 Correlation of Metrics

Using the data gathered from Section 5.4.2, we can perform the Kendall τ test (see Section 2.9.2) to make an educated claim for the correlation of different metrics. For our evaluation we made use of 20,000 randomly selected candidates from our evolutionary runs. This leads to a standard deviation of $\sqrt{\frac{4*20,000+10}{9*20,000*20,000-9*20,000}} = 0.004714222$. Our interval for accepting the null hypothesis with 99% confidence is thus defined as $[-2.58*0.004714222/\sqrt{20000}, 2.58*0.004714222/\sqrt{20000}] = [-0.00008600752, 0.00008600752]$. This means, that for any pair of metrics, we can say that, if they are independent, they have to have a Kendall τ coefficient in that range with 99% certainty. In our case, we do not accept that null hypothesis for any pair of metrics. All of our metrics are somewhat correlated. What stands out though, is that there exists a perfect correlation between the super step version and the regular version of the metrics $R2$, $R3$, and $R4$. This means that these metrics provide the exact same information as their super step versions, leaving us to decide based on runtime, which metric to prefer.

5.5.3 Qualitative Evaluation

When observing the evolved solutions we were able to determine that for all new metrics, there were still consistent / realizable solution candidates generated. This means, that none of these metrics, when optimized for, inhibits the evolutionary algorithm from providing good, realizable solutions to the requirements engineer. This alleviates our concern, as all of the provided metrics, when run with successfully, achieve the specified goal 1. However, as stated in Section 5.5.1, some SML specifications can be very complex, which leads to the metric $R5$ (see Section 4.2.3) causing memory exceptions during runtime. As such, we do not recommend $R5$ for active evolutionary runs right now.

Regarding the second goal of finding out which of the metrics might perform better or worse than others, we found, that the super steps versions of either metric lead to equivalent results compared to the respective metric when calculated without super steps.

We also pitched our recommended restrictiveness metrics against each other in direct comparison but were not able to narrow down the set of recommended metrics, as each of them performed equally well.

5.5.4 Summary and Recommendation

During our evaluation, we found important insights into the advantages and disadvantages of our proposed restrictiveness metrics. We found, that the super steps version of no metric lead to measurably worse results than the original version of that metric. Given that, we can safely recommend, that if you were to use the metrics $R5$, $R6$, or $R7$, you should do so only with the super steps adjustment, since those can be calculated significantly faster. Since this was the opposite for the metrics $R2$, $R3$, and $R4$, we recommend using those without the super step adjustment.

We also found that none of the metrics pose a conceivable threat to the runtime of the evolutionary generation (see Section 5.4.1). Especially the effect of the metrics $R1$, $R2$, $R3$ and $R4$ on the runtime is barely noticeable.

Due to the highly likely independence of $R1$ from all of the other metrics, we believe, that this local penalty metric does not represent environment restrictiveness, as all other metrics seem to more or less correlate. As such we recommend not relying on $R1$ and picking one of the other metrics instead.

Since $R5$ leads to runtime errors in some cases (see Section 5.5.1), we do not recommend this metric as well.

Although they did produce similar results, we have reasons to believe that $R2$ and $R3$ could in theory perform worse than $R4$ due to their weaknesses in regards to certain edge cases (see Section 4.2.1). Due to this, we recommend using $R4$ over $R3$ and $R2$.

Combining all that, we are left with the following metrics: $R4$, $R6_S$, $R7_S$. As explained in Section 5.4.3, none of them seems to outperform the others, as all of them produce similar results. This leads us to believe, that $R4$ is the superior metric, simply due to its significantly lower runtime.

Future Work

While we already investigated plenty of different approaches towards identifying the best candidate for restrictiveness, there are still some left for further research.

6.1 Environment Violations

A big topic for further research towards restrictiveness are different strategies to incorporate the notion of *well separation* (see Definition 2.21). We presented this topic in Section 4.3.3 as a way to improve the restrictiveness metrics, but we were not able to implement it as a part of this project. To include environment violations into the evolutionary algorithm one could go several different ways:

- Establish a new (fourth) objective, that resembles a penalty for any environment violation. Optimizing towards this objective and our new restrictiveness metric at the same time but via different dimensions could yield good results for both objectives.
- One could also try to incorporate the penalty value into the existing restrictiveness metric. Our extension of the MOEA framework allows for arbitrary data types for an objective, instead of just a single double/integer value, as long as a dedicated comparator is provided to compare two candidate solutions regarding this new datatype. Utilizing this new feature, one could set up a new datatype (and matching comparator), to set up different logical tiebreaks or weights for the two distinct values of the optimization target and thus optimize for low restrictiveness and a low number of environment violations at the same time.
- The last approach towards recognizing environment violations would be to go even further and define well-separation as a constraint for sound solutions. This would elevate the importance of the environment violations and help in creating solutions, where the environment can never reach states from which there is no sound continuation of events.

Which of these approaches is best befitting for the topic of environment violations is not clear at this point. Future research could investigate how to incorporate this additional information which ultimately benefits the quality of the evolutionary algorithm.

6.2 Additional metric candidates

Due to our limited time, we were not able to implement all of the proposed metric candidates in Section 4.4. In particular, the original weakness measure (see Section 4.2.5) by Cavezza et

al. (without our simplification), relying on the complement of the given SML specification, would be interesting. In their paper, Cavezza et al. show, that there are cases, in which the simplified weakness measure does not suffice, and the hausdorff dimension of the complement of the specification is necessary as a way to decide between different solutions. It would be interesting to implement this weakness measure as a metric for restrictiveness and evaluate it for efficiency and performance. Maybe the original weakness measure can produce better results than our simplified version.

Apart from that, there might be other metrics, that can be useful to develop a notion of environment restrictiveness, that we have not thought of. If a new metric were to be defined and implemented it could easily be evaluated by incorporating it into the code base and running our evaluation again to find out if this new metric can provide any benefits.

6.3 Additional Evaluation

Not only implementing and evaluation of the regular weakness measure could be part of future research. Since the hausdorff dimension of the complement of the given specification becomes relevant only if both, entropy and hausdorff dimension of the original specification can not decide between two candidate solutions, we believe that measuring how often this particular case happens during a regular evolution is interesting as well. If e.g., one were to find out, that this does happen only in very few edge cases, the evolutionary algorithm with its inherent randomness could be sufficient as is. Implementing the original weakness measure and applying it to the evolution might not be desired after all due to the additional computational overhead. This question could be asked for the simplified weakness measure as well. Maybe the entropy - part of the weakness measure is sufficient for deciding between two candidate solutions most of the time and the computation of the hausdorff dimension is not necessary here.

Additional Evaluation of Quality Apart from this new goal, one could also run some additional evaluation to find out about the relation between the different metrics in more detail. In our evaluation, we relied on plotting the performance of the restrictiveness metrics and comparing them directly to find any obvious differences. We believe that other techniques for comparing the performance of certain metrics to others can help to find more subtle results. As a starting point for that research, we recommend the "A measure of stochastic superiority" by Vargha & Delaney [VD00], which might be able to find a definitive "best" metric out of our preferred 3 ($R4$, $R6_S$, $R7_S$) and put a number on how much better exactly that "best" metric might be.

Another approach towards measuring the quality of the metrics could be to find out what effect they might have on the other existing objectives. For this one could set up a hypervolume measurement over all given objectives and investigate the changes, that applying a certain restrictiveness metric has on the generation. This investigation could focus on the overall hypervolume or the first two objectives ("evolved assumption size" and "Environment related proportion") in particular.

6.4 Parameterizing the search algorithm

During our evaluation, we invoked the search algorithm with multiple different parameters until we ultimately found some that performed well for our use case. Additional research could be of use so that one can find out which parameterization fits best for certain specifications. This could mean either focus on a fast and efficient search for a somewhat alright solution or prioritizing thoroughness and finding the best possible solution with the least amount of effort. If done right,

one could possibly provide a guide for requirements engineers on how to utilize the generation command-line interface of Schmelter et al. to achieve a "best" result depending on their needs.

6.5 Additional SML Examples for Evaluation

In this thesis, we were able to perform our evaluation on just two SML research examples: "*Production Cell*" (see Appendix A.1) and "*EBEAS*" (see Appendix A.2). Since our approach is ultimately random and since we performed a significant amount of runs, we are fairly certain, that the data we analyzed is sufficient to make general claims about the different restrictiveness metrics. Still, additional evaluation based on other examples could be useful to either confirm our results or even refute them and provoke more research towards other approaches.

6.5 ADDITIONAL SML EXAMPLES FOR EVALUATION

Conclusion

Throughout this project, we managed to gain insights not only from a scientific point of view but also from a learning perspective. We take this opportunity to summarize what we have done so far, which scientifically interesting findings we were able to make, and how we were able to contribute to the topic.

7.1 Problem Statement

While the original problem of assisting requirement engineers is already addressed by the evolutionary algorithm by Schmelter et al., we sought to improve this algorithm. Our goal was to have it generate the specific kind of solutions / assumptions, that restrict the environment the least, so that the evolved specifications, that are generated, allow for more general environments making the SUT more generally applicable. This also serves to prevent overfitting the generated specifications to the constraint of realizability. Schmelter et al. already provide an initial candidate for that, for which we point out potential flaws in the introduction (see Section 1.3) with the help of our running example - "Production Cell" (see Appendix A.1). We point out that the most important problem with this kind of metric is that it can only compare the different generated assumptions directly without taking into account the bigger picture. We interpret it as a rather local approach. To find a better metric for restrictiveness of the environment we utilize the state graph, which is created during an automatic realizability check of the SML specification. This analysis is already performed during the evolutionary algorithm by Schmelter et al. to evaluate new solution candidates for consistency.

7.2 Contribution

With this state graph, we were able to rely on multiple different graph measures to evaluate the complexity / restrictiveness of the specification as a whole. We created individual adjustments for some of these metrics and incorporated the notion of *super steps* as an adjustment for all of them. This helps to fit the metrics to our use case of measuring only the restrictiveness of the exact part of the graph, that describes the possible behavior of the environment, rather than the restrictiveness of the entire SML specification. We then implemented the conceptualized metrics for environment restrictiveness and incorporated them in the existing evolutionary algorithm by Schmelter et al., which enabled us to show that these concepts work for SML specifications in practice as well. We evaluated the different metrics with the help of a case study using

two existing research examples ("Production Cell" and "EBEAS") to investigate and validate their behavior using real SML specifications. During this evaluation, we found out about the individual advantages and disadvantages of the restrictiveness metrics in regards to runtime and quality. We were also able to find and compare correlations between them. In the end, this evaluation enables us to now make an educated recommendation for which metric to use in the future.

7.3 Scientific Findings

We were able to find out that, although the notion of the hausdorff dimension ($R6^1$) and weakness ($R7^2$) are more thorough and complete in theory, the much simpler approach of measuring the number of decisions the environment can make ($R4^3$) suffices for the evolutionary generation with utmost certainty (see Section 5.5.4). With this approach, the evolutionary generation performs significantly faster (see Section 5.5.1) than with the metrics of comparable quality. It also leads to the generation of much less restrictive assumptions than not optimizing for restrictiveness at all or relying on the former notion of local penalty values ($R1$) for new assumptions (see Section 5.5.3). With this in mind, we recommend using the metric $R4$ as the metric for restrictiveness during the evolutionary generation.

¹see Section 4.2.4

²see Section 4.2.5

³see Section 4.2.2

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SML Examples

A.1 Production Cell

A.1.1 SML - Code

```
1 import 'productioncell.ecore'
2
3 specification ProductionCellSpecification {
4     domain productioncell
5
6     controllable {
7         Controller
8     }
9
10    non-spontaneous events {
11        Controller.arrivedAtTable
12        Controller.arrivedAtPress
13        Controller.arrivedAtDepositBelt
14        Controller.pressingFinished
15    }
16
17    collaboration ProcessPlate {
18
19        static role Controller controller
20        static role ArmA armA
21        static role ArmB armB
22        static role Press press
23        static role TableSensor tableSensor
24
25        // Arm A related system guarantees
26
27        guarantee scenario NewBlankArrived {
28            tableSensor->controller.blankArrived
29            strict urgent controller->controller.setBlankAtTable(true)
30            strict urgent controller->armA.moveToTable
31        }
32
33        guarantee scenario PickupBlankAndTransportToPress {
34            armA->controller.arrivedAtTable
35            interrupt [!controller.blankAtTable]
36            strict urgent controller->armA.pickUp
37            strict urgent controller->controller.setBlankAtTable(false)
38            strict urgent controller->armA.moveToPress
39        }
40
41        guarantee scenario ArmAReleaseBlankAndPress {
42            armA->controller.arrivedAtPress
43            strict urgent controller->armA.releaseBlank
44            strict urgent controller->press.press
45            strict urgent controller->armA.moveToTable
46        }
47
48        // Arm B related system guarantees
```

```

49
50   guarantee scenario NewPlatePressed {
51     press->controller.pressingFinished
52     strict urgent controller->armB.moveToPress
53   }
54
55   guarantee scenario ArmBPickupPlateAndTransportToDepositBelt {
56     armB->controller.arrivedAtPress
57     strict urgent controller->armB.pickUp
58     strict urgent controller->armB.moveToDepositBelt
59   }
60
61   guarantee scenario ArmBReleasePlateAndMoveToPress {
62     armB->controller.arrivedAtDepositBelt
63     strict urgent controller->armB.releasePlate
64   }
65
66   //general assumptions
67
68   // ArmA assumptions
69   assumption scenario ArmAArrivesAtTable {
70     controller->armA.moveToTable()
71     strict eventually armA->controller.arrivedAtTable()
72   } constraints [
73     forbidden armA->controller.arrivedAtPress()
74   ]
75
76   assumption scenario ArmAArrivesAtPress {
77     controller->armA.moveToPress()
78     strict eventually armA->controller.arrivedAtPress
79   } constraints [
80     forbidden armA->controller.arrivedAtTable()
81   ]
82
83   // ArmB assumptions
84   assumption scenario ArmBArrivesAtDepositBelt {
85     controller->armB.moveToDepositBelt()
86     strict eventually armB->controller.arrivedAtDepositBelt
87   } constraints [
88     forbidden armB->controller.arrivedAtPress()
89   ]
90
91   assumption scenario ArmBArrivesAtPress {
92     controller->armB.moveToPress()
93     strict eventually armB->controller.arrivedAtPress
94   } constraints [
95     forbidden armB->controller.arrivedAtDepositBelt()
96   ]
97
98   // Press assumptions
99   assumption scenario PressActuallyPresses {
100     controller->press.press
101     strict eventually press->controller.pressingFinished
102   }
103
104   //safety guarantees
105
106   guarantee scenario ArmsMustNotCollideAtPress1 {
107     controller->armA.moveToPress
108     monitored eventually controller->armA.moveToTable
109   } constraints [
110     forbidden controller->armB.moveToPress()
111   ]
112
113   guarantee scenario ArmsMustNotCollideAtPress2 {
114     controller->armB.moveToPress
115     monitored eventually controller->armB.moveToDepositBelt
116   } constraints [
117     forbidden controller->armA.moveToPress()
118   ]
119
120   // safety assumptions (sample solution)
121   // assumption scenario BlanksArriveSlowly {
122   //   tableSensor->controller.blankArrived
123   //   monitored eventually controller->armB.releasePlate
124   // } constraints [
125   //   forbidden tableSensor->controller.blankArrived()
126   // ]

```

```

127 }
128 }

```

A.1.2 Production Rules (cspec)

```

1 import "productioncell.sml" as productioncell_sml
2 import "productioncell.ecore" as productioncell_ecore
3 import "http://www.scenariotools.org/sml" as sml_mm
4 import "http://www.scenariotools.org/sml/expressions/ScenarioExpressions
  " as sml_exp_mm
5
6 Grammar default {
7
8   [ <scenarios> ]
9
10  <scenarios> := (<scenarios> <scenario>) | <scenario>
11
12  <scenario> := compose sml_mm.sml.Scenario : sml_mm.sml.Scenario {
13    kind = sml_mm.sml.ScenarioKind.assumption;
14    ownedInteraction = <root_interaction>;
15  }
16  [target: productioncell_sml.ProductionCellSpecification.ProcessPlate
  feature: scenarios]
17
18  <root_interaction> := compose sml_mm.sml.Interaction :
19  sml_mm.sml.Interaction {
20    fragments = (<initial_message> <message_interaction>);
21    constraints = <constraints>;
22  }
23
24  // initial messages
25
26  <initial_message> := compose sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage : // initial
  environment message
27  <armA2controller_message_template> | //
28  <armB2controller_message_template> | //
29  <press2controller_message_template> | //
30  <tableSensor2controller_message_template> | //
31  // initial system messages
32  <controller2armA_message_template> | //
33  <controller2armB_message_template> | //
34  <controller2press_message_template>
35
36  // environment message templates
37
38  <armA2controller_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.Message {
39    modelElement = <armA2controller_events>;
40    sender = productioncell_sml.ProductionCellSpecification.
  ProcessPlate.armA;
41    receiver = productioncell_sml.ProductionCellSpecification.
  ProcessPlate.controller;
42  }
43  <armB2controller_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.Message {
44    modelElement = <armB2controller_events>;

```

```

45     sender = productioncell_sml.ProductionCellSpecification.
46         ProcessPlate.armB;
47     receiver = productioncell_sml.ProductionCellSpecification.
48         ProcessPlate.controller;
49 }
50 <press2controller_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.Message {
51     modelElement = <press2controller_events>;
52     sender = productioncell_sml.ProductionCellSpecification.
53         ProcessPlate.press;
54     receiver = productioncell_sml.ProductionCellSpecification.
55         ProcessPlate.controller;
56 }
57 <tableSensor2controller_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.Message {
58     modelElement = <tableSensor2controller_events>;
59     sender = productioncell_sml.ProductionCellSpecification.
60         ProcessPlate.tableSensor;
61     receiver = productioncell_sml.ProductionCellSpecification.
62         ProcessPlate.controller;
63 }
64 // system message templates
65 <controller2armA_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.Message {
66     modelElement = <controller2armA_events>;
67     sender = productioncell_sml.ProductionCellSpecification.
68         ProcessPlate.controller;
69     receiver = productioncell_sml.ProductionCellSpecification.
70         ProcessPlate.armA;
71 }
72 <controller2armB_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.Message {
73     modelElement = <controller2armB_events>;
74     sender = productioncell_sml.ProductionCellSpecification.
75         ProcessPlate.controller;
76     receiver = productioncell_sml.ProductionCellSpecification.
77         ProcessPlate.armB;
78 }
79 <controller2press_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.Message {
80     modelElement = <controller2press_events>;
81     sender = productioncell_sml.ProductionCellSpecification.
82         ProcessPlate.controller;
83     receiver = productioncell_sml.ProductionCellSpecification.
84         ProcessPlate.press;
85 }
86 // environment events
87 <armA2controller_events> := productioncell_ecore.productioncell.
88     Controller.arrivedAtPress | //
89 productioncell_ecore.productioncell.Controller.arrivedAtTable
90 <armB2controller_events> := productioncell_ecore.productioncell.
91     Controller.arrivedAtPress | //
92 productioncell_ecore.productioncell.Controller.arrivedAtDepositBelt

```

```

87   <press2controller_events> := productioncell_ecore.productioncell.
      Controller.pressingFinished
88
89   <tableSensor2controller_events> := productioncell_ecore.
      productioncell.Controller.blankArrived
90
91   // system events
92
93   <controller2armA_events> := productioncell_ecore.productioncell.ArmA
      .pickUp | //
94   productioncell_ecore.productioncell.ArmA.moveToPress | //
95   productioncell_ecore.productioncell.ArmA.releaseBlank | //
96   productioncell_ecore.productioncell.ArmA.moveToTable
97
98   <controller2armB_events> := productioncell_ecore.productioncell.ArmB
      .pickUp | //
99   productioncell_ecore.productioncell.ArmB.moveToDepositBelt | //
100  productioncell_ecore.productioncell.ArmB.releasePlate | //
101  productioncell_ecore.productioncell.ArmB.moveToPress
102
103  <controller2press_events> := productioncell_ecore.productioncell.
      Press.press
104
105  // modal messages
106
107  <message_interaction> := (<message_interaction> <modal_message>) | <
      modal_message>
108
109  <modal_message> := compose sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage : // model
      environment messages
110  <armA2controller_message_template> <strict> <
      environment_expectation_kind> | //
111  <armB2controller_message_template> <strict> <
      environment_expectation_kind> | //
112  <press2controller_message_template> <strict> <
      environment_expectation_kind> | //
113  <tableSensor2controller_message_template> <strict> <
      environment_expectation_kind> | //
114  // modal system messages
115  <controller2armA_message_template> <strict> <system_expectation_kind
      > | //
116  <controller2armB_message_template> <strict> <system_expectation_kind
      > | //
117  <controller2press_message_template> <strict> <
      system_expectation_kind>
118
119  // modal message properties
120
121  <strict> := sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage {
122      strict = true | false;
123  }
124
125  <environment_expectation_kind> := <committed_message_template> | //
126  // <monitored_committed_message_template> | //
127  <eventually_message_template> | //
128  <monitored_eventually_message_template> | //

```

```

129 NOOP
130
131 <system_expectation_kind> :=
132 // <monitored_committed_message_template> | //
133 // <monitored_urgent_message_template> | //
134 // <monitored_requested_message_template> | //
135 <monitored_eventually_message_template>
136
137 <committed_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage {
138     expectationKind = sml_mm.sml.ExpectationKind.committed;
139 }
140
141 <urgent_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage {
142     expectationKind = sml_mm.sml.ExpectationKind.urgent;
143 }
144
145 <requested_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage {
146     expectationKind = sml_mm.sml.ExpectationKind.requested;
147 }
148
149 <eventually_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage {
150     expectationKind = sml_mm.sml.ExpectationKind.eventually;
151 }
152
153 <monitored_committed_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage {
154     monitored = true;
155     expectationKind = sml_mm.sml.ExpectationKind.committed;
156 }
157
158 <monitored_urgent_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage {
159     monitored = true;
160     expectationKind = sml_mm.sml.ExpectationKind.urgent;
161 }
162
163 <monitored_requested_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage {
164     monitored = true;
165     expectationKind = sml_mm.sml.ExpectationKind.requested;
166 }
167
168 <monitored_eventually_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage {
169     monitored = true;
170     expectationKind = sml_mm.sml.ExpectationKind.eventually;
171 }
172
173 // // last messages in a scenario
174 //
175 // <last_message> := <last_armA2controller_message> | //
176 // <last_armB2controller_message> | //
177 // <last_press2controller_message> | //
178 // <last_tableSensor2controller_message> | //
179 // <last_controller2armA_message> | //
180 // <last_controller2armB_message> | //
181 // <last_controller2press_message>
182 //
183 // // last environment messages
184 //

```

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```

185 // <last_armA2controller_message> := compose sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage <
      armA2controller_message_template> <strict> <
      last_environment_expectation_kind>
186 // <last_armB2controller_message> := compose sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage <
      armB2controller_message_template> <strict> <
      last_environment_expectation_kind>
187 // <last_press2controller_message> := compose sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage <
      press2controller_message_template> <strict> <
      last_environment_expectation_kind>
188 // <last_tableSensor2controller_message> := compose sml_mm.sml.
      ModalMessage <tableSensor2controller_message_template> <strict> <
      last_environment_expectation_kind>
189 //
190 // // last system messages
191 //
192 // <last_controller2armA_message> := compose sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage <
      controller2armA_message_template> <strict> <
      last_system_expectation_kind>
193 // <last_controller2armB_message> := compose sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage <
      controller2armB_message_template> <strict> <
      last_system_expectation_kind>
194 // <last_controller2press_message> := compose sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage <
      controller2press_message_template> <strict> <
      last_system_expectation_kind>
195 //
196 // // allowed expectation kinds for last messages in a scenario
197 //
198 // <last_environment_expectation_kind> := <committed_message_template>
      | //
199 // <eventually_message_template> | //
200 // NOOP
201 //
202 // <last_system_expectation_kind> := <
      monitored_requested_message_template>
203
204 // constraints
205
206 <constraints> := compose sml_mm.sml.ConstraintBlock : sml_mm.sml.
      ConstraintBlock {
207     forbidden = <forbidden_messages>;
208 }
209
210 // forbidden environment messages
211
212 <forbidden_messages> := <forbidden_messages> <forbidden_message> | <
      forbidden_message> | NOOP
213
214 <forbidden_message> := compose sml_mm.sml.Message :
215 <armA2controller_message_template> | //
216 <armB2controller_message_template> | //
217 <press2controller_message_template> | //
218 <tableSensor2controller_message_template>
219 }

```

A.2 EBEAS

A.2.1 SML - Code

```

1 import 'ebeas.ecore'
2
3 specification EbeasSpecification{
4     domain ebeas
5
6     controllable {
7         EBEAS
8     }
9
10    non-spontaneous events {
11        EBEAS.emcyBrakeResponse
12        EBEAS.evadeResponse
13        EBEAS.emcyControlled
14    }
15
16    collaboration HandleEmergency {
17
18        static role EBEAS ebeas
19        static role EgoVehicle egoVehicle
20        static role OvertakerVehicle overtakerVehicle
21        static role RearVehicle rearVehicle
22
23        // Emergency Braking
24        guarantee scenario EmergencyBraking {
25            egoVehicle->ebeas.obstacle
26            strict urgent ebeas->rearVehicle.emcyBrakeRequest
27        }
28
29        // Emergency Braking Response
30        assumption scenario EmcyBrakingRequestResponses {
31            ebeas->rearVehicle.emcyBrakeRequest
32            alternative {
33                rearVehicle->ebeas.emcyBrakeResponse(true)
34            } or {
35                rearVehicle->ebeas.emcyBrakeResponse(false)
36            }
37        }
38
39        guarantee scenario EmcyBrakingRequestResponsePositive {
40            rearVehicle->ebeas.emcyBrakeResponse(true)
41            strict urgent ebeas->egoVehicle.emcyBraking
42        }
43
44        assumption scenario EmcyBrakingResponse {
45            ebeas->egoVehicle.emcyBraking
46            eventually egoVehicle->ebeas.emcyControlled
47        }
48
49        // Emergency Evasion
50        guarantee scenario EmcyBrakingRequestResponseNegative {
51            rearVehicle->ebeas.emcyBrakeResponse(false)
52            strict urgent ebeas->overtakerVehicle.evadeRequest
53        }
54
55        assumption scenario EvadeRequestResponses {
56            ebeas->overtakerVehicle.evadeRequest
57            alternative {
58                overtakerVehicle->ebeas.evadeResponse(true)
59            } or {
60                overtakerVehicle->ebeas.evadeResponse(false)
61            }
62        }
63
64        guarantee scenario EvadeCoordinationPositive {
65            overtakerVehicle->ebeas.evadeResponse(true)
66            strict urgent ebeas->egoVehicle.evade
67            strict urgent ebeas->overtakerVehicle.evadeWarning
68        }
69
70        guarantee scenario EvadeCoordinationNegative {
71            overtakerVehicle->ebeas.evadeResponse(false)
72            strict urgent ebeas->egoVehicle.preCrash
73        }

```

```

74 |
75 |     assumption scenario EvadeResponse {
76 |         ebeas->egoVehicle.evade
77 |         eventually egoVehicle->ebeas.emcyControlled
78 |     }
79 |
80 |     assumption scenario Crash {
81 |         ebeas->egoVehicle.preCrash
82 |         eventually egoVehicle->ebeas.emcyControlled
83 |     }
84 |
85 |     // Safety Requirements
86 |
87 |     guarantee scenario ForbidEmergencyBrakingDuringEvasion {
88 |         ebeas->egoVehicle.evade
89 |         monitored eventually ebeas->egoVehicle.emcyBraking
90 |         violation [true]
91 |     } constraints [
92 |         interrupt egoVehicle->ebeas.emcyControlled()
93 |     ]
94 |
95 |     guarantee scenario ForbidEvasionDuringEmergencyBraking {
96 |         ebeas->egoVehicle.emcyBraking
97 |         monitored eventually ebeas->egoVehicle.evade
98 |         violation [true]
99 |     } constraints [
100 |         interrupt egoVehicle->ebeas.emcyControlled()
101 |     ]
102 |
103 |     // sample solution
104 |     assumption scenario GeneralEnvironmentAssumptions {
105 |         // egoVehicle->ebeas.obstacle
106 |         // monitored eventually egoVehicle->ebeas.emcyControlled()
107 |     }
108 |     // constraints [
109 |     //     forbidden egoVehicle->ebeas.obstacle()
110 |     // ]
111 | }
112 |

```

A.2.2 Production Rules (cspec)

```

1 | import "ebeas.sml" as ebeas_sml
2 | import "ebeas.ecore" as ebeas_ecore
3 | import "http://www.scenariotools.org/sml" as sml_mm
4 | import "http://www.scenariotools.org/sml/expressions/ScenarioExpressions
   |     " as sml_exp_mm
5 |
6 | Grammar default {
7 |
8 |     [ <scenarios> ]
9 |
10 |     <scenarios> := (<scenarios> <scenario>) | <scenario>
11 |
12 |     <scenario> := compose sml_mm.sml.Scenario : sml_mm.sml.Scenario {
13 |         kind = sml_mm.sml.ScenarioKind.assumption;
14 |         ownedInteraction = <root_interaction>;
15 |     }
16 |     [target: ebeas_sml.EbeasSpecification.HandleEmergency feature:
   |         scenarios /*featureXPath: "./scenarios"*/]
17 |
18 |     <root_interaction> := compose sml_mm.sml.Interaction :
19 |     sml_mm.sml.Interaction {
20 |         fragments = <initial_message> <message_interaction>;
21 |         constraints = <constraints>;
22 |     }

```

```

23
24 // initial messages
25
26 <initial_message> := compose sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage : //
27 // initial environment messages
28 <base_egoVehicle2ebeas_message> | //
29 <base_rearVehicle2ebeas_message> | //
30 <base_overtakerVehicle2ebeas_message> | //
31 // initial system messages
32 <base_ebeas2egoVehicle_message> | //
33 <base_ebeas2rearVehicle_message> | //
34 <base_ebeas2overtakerVehicle_message>
35
36 // base environment messages
37
38 <base_egoVehicle2ebeas_message> :=
39 (<egoVehicle2ebeas_message_roles>
40 sml_mm.sml.Message {
41     modelElement = <egoVehicle2ebeas_no_parameter_events>;
42 })
43
44 <base_rearVehicle2ebeas_message> :=
45 <rearVehicle2ebeas_message_roles>
46 sml_mm.sml.Message {
47     modelElement = <rearVehicle2ebeas_boolean_parameter_events>;
48     parameters = <boolean_msg_parameter>;
49 }
50
51 <base_overtakerVehicle2ebeas_message> :=
52 <overtakerVehicle2ebeas_message_roles>
53 sml_mm.sml.Message {
54     modelElement = <overtakerVehicle2ebeas_boolean_parameter_events
55     >;
56     parameters = <boolean_msg_parameter>;
57 }
58 // base system messages
59
60 <base_ebeas2egoVehicle_message> :=
61 <ebeas2egoVehicle_message_roles>
62 sml_mm.sml.Message {
63     modelElement = <ebeas2egoVehicle_no_parameter_events>;
64 }
65
66 <base_ebeas2rearVehicle_message> :=
67 <ebeas2rearVehicle_message_roles>
68 sml_mm.sml.Message {
69     modelElement = <ebeas2rearVehicle_no_parameter_events>;
70 }
71
72 <base_ebeas2overtakerVehicle_message> :=
73 <ebeas2overtakerVehicle_message_roles>
74 sml_mm.sml.Message {
75     modelElement = <ebeas2overtakerVehicle_no_parameter_events>;
76 }
77

```

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```

78 // environment message templates
79
80 <egoVehicle2ebeas_message_roles> := sml_mm.sml.Message {
81     sender = ebeas_sml.EbeasSpecification.HandleEmergency.egoVehicle
82         ;
83     receiver = ebeas_sml.EbeasSpecification.HandleEmergency.ebeas;
84 }
85
86 <rearVehicle2ebeas_message_roles> := sml_mm.sml.Message {
87     sender = ebeas_sml.EbeasSpecification.HandleEmergency.
88         rearVehicle;
89     receiver = ebeas_sml.EbeasSpecification.HandleEmergency.ebeas;
90 }
91
92 <overtakerVehicle2ebeas_message_roles> := sml_mm.sml.Message {
93     sender = ebeas_sml.EbeasSpecification.HandleEmergency.
94         overtakerVehicle;
95     receiver = ebeas_sml.EbeasSpecification.HandleEmergency.ebeas;
96 }
97
98 // system message templates
99
100 <ebeas2egoVehicle_message_roles> := sml_mm.sml.Message {
101     sender = ebeas_sml.EbeasSpecification.HandleEmergency.ebeas;
102     receiver = ebeas_sml.EbeasSpecification.HandleEmergency.
103         egoVehicle;
104 }
105
106 <ebeas2rearVehicle_message_roles> := sml_mm.sml.Message {
107     sender = ebeas_sml.EbeasSpecification.HandleEmergency.ebeas;
108     receiver = ebeas_sml.EbeasSpecification.HandleEmergency.
109         rearVehicle;
110 }
111
112 <ebeas2overtakerVehicle_message_roles> := sml_mm.sml.Message {
113     sender = ebeas_sml.EbeasSpecification.HandleEmergency.ebeas;
114     receiver = ebeas_sml.EbeasSpecification.HandleEmergency.
115         overtakerVehicle;
116 }
117
118 <message_interaction> := <message_interaction> <modal_message> | <
119     modal_message>
120
121 // modal messages
122
123 <modal_message> := compose sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage : // modal
124     environment messages
125 <base_egoVehicle2ebeas_message> <strict> <
126     environment_expectation_kind> | //
127 <base_rearVehicle2ebeas_message> <strict> <
128     environment_expectation_kind> | //
129 <base_overtakerVehicle2ebeas_message> <strict> <
130     environment_expectation_kind> | //
131 // modal system messages
132 <base_ebeas2egoVehicle_message> <strict> <system_expectation_kind> |
133 //

```

```

122 <base_ebeas2rearVehicle_message> <strict> <system_expectation_kind>
    | //
123 <base_ebeas2overtakerVehicle_message> <strict> <
    system_expectation_kind>
124
125 // constraints
126
127 <constraints> := compose sml_mm.sml.ConstraintBlock : sml_mm.sml.
    ConstraintBlock {
128     forbidden = <forbidden_messages>;
129 }
130
131 // forbidden environment messages
132
133 <forbidden_messages> := <forbidden_messages> <forbidden_message> | <
    forbidden_message> | NOOP
134
135 <forbidden_message> := compose sml_mm.sml.Message :
136 <base_egoVehicle2ebeas_message> | //
137 <base_rearVehicle2ebeas_message> | //
138 <base_overtakerVehicle2ebeas_message>
139
140 // environment events
141
142 <egoVehicle2ebeas_no_parameter_events> := ebeas_ecore.ebeas.EBEAS.
    obstacle | //
143 ebeas_ecore.ebeas.EBEAS.emcyControlled
144
145 <rearVehicle2ebeas_boolean_parameter_events> := ebeas_ecore.ebeas.
    EBEAS.emcyBrakeResponse
146
147 <overtakerVehicle2ebeas_boolean_parameter_events> := ebeas_ecore.
    ebeas.EBEAS.evadeResponse
148
149 // system events
150
151 <ebeas2egoVehicle_no_parameter_events> := ebeas_ecore.ebeas.
    EgoVehicle.emcyBraking | //
152 ebeas_ecore.ebeas.EgoVehicle.evade // |
153 ebeas_ecore.ebeas.EgoVehicle.preCrash
154
155 <ebeas2rearVehicle_no_parameter_events> := ebeas_ecore.ebeas.
    RearVehicle.emcyBrakeRequest | //
156 ebeas_ecore.ebeas.RearVehicle.emcyBrakeWarning
157
158 <ebeas2overtakerVehicle_no_parameter_events> := ebeas_ecore.ebeas.
    OvertakerVehicle.evadeRequest | //
159 ebeas_ecore.ebeas.OvertakerVehicle.evadeWarning
160
161 // helper templates
162
163 <boolean_msg_parameter> := compose sml_mm.sml.ParameterBinding :
    sml_mm.sml.ParameterBinding {
164     bindingExpression = <boolean_value_parameter_expression>;
165 }
166

```

CHAPTER A. SML EXAMPLES

```

167 <boolean_value_parameter_expression> := compose sml_mm.sml.
      ValueParameterExpression : sml_mm.sml.ValueParameterExpression {
168     value = <boolean_value>;
169 }
170
171 <boolean_value> := compose sml_exp_mm.scenarioExpressions.
      BooleanValue : sml_exp_mm.scenarioExpressions.BooleanValue {
172     value = true | false;
173 }
174
175 <true_msg_parameter> := compose sml_mm.sml.ParameterBinding : sml_mm
      .sml.ParameterBinding {
176     bindingExpression = <true_value_parameter_expression>;
177 }
178
179 <true_value_parameter_expression> := compose sml_mm.sml.
      ValueParameterExpression : sml_mm.sml.ValueParameterExpression {
180     value = <true_value_template>;
181 }
182
183 <true_value_template> := compose sml_exp_mm.scenarioExpressions.
      BooleanValue : sml_exp_mm.scenarioExpressions.BooleanValue {
184     value = true;
185 }
186
187 <violation_fragment> := compose sml_mm.sml.ViolationCondition :
      sml_mm.sml.ViolationCondition {
188     conditionExpression = <condition_expression>;
189 }
190
191 <condition_expression> := compose sml_mm.sml.ConditionExpression :
      sml_mm.sml.ConditionExpression {
192     expression = <boolean_value>;
193 }
194
195 <boolean_parameter_message> := sml_mm.sml.Message {
196     parameters = <boolean_msg_parameter>;
197 }
198
199 <true_parameter_message> := sml_mm.sml.Message {
200     parameters = <true_msg_parameter>;
201 }
202
203 // modal message properties
204
205 <strict> := sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage {
206     strict = true | false;
207 }
208
209 <environment_expectation_kind> := <committed_message_template> | //
210 <eventually_message_template> | //
211 <monitored_eventually_message_template> | //
212 NOOP
213
214 <system_expectation_kind> :=
215 <monitored_eventually_message_template>

```

```
216
217 <committed_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage {
218     expectationKind = sml_mm.sml.ExpectationKind.committed;
219 }
220
221 <urgent_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage {
222     expectationKind = sml_mm.sml.ExpectationKind.urgent;
223 }
224
225 <requested_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage {
226     expectationKind = sml_mm.sml.ExpectationKind.requested;
227 }
228
229 <eventually_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage {
230     expectationKind = sml_mm.sml.ExpectationKind.eventually;
231 }
232
233 <monitored_committed_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage {
234     monitored = true;
235     expectationKind = sml_mm.sml.ExpectationKind.committed;
236 }
237
238 <monitored_urgent_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage {
239     monitored = true;
240     expectationKind = sml_mm.sml.ExpectationKind.urgent;
241 }
242
243 <monitored_requested_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage {
244     monitored = true;
245     expectationKind = sml_mm.sml.ExpectationKind.requested;
246 }
247
248 <monitored_eventually_message_template> := sml_mm.sml.ModalMessage {
249     monitored = true;
250     expectationKind = sml_mm.sml.ExpectationKind.eventually;
251 }
252 }
```

B

Stategraph Example for Production Cell

Figure B.1: Extract of the stategraph for a single validation of the original, faulty production cell specification.

Figure B.3: Full stategraph resulting from the validation of the production cell specification after applying solutionB.

C.1 Metric Performances

Figure C.1: Metric Performance - Production Cell

C.1 METRIC PERFORMANCES

CHAPTER C. EVALUATION

C.1 METRIC PERFORMANCES

CHAPTER C. EVALUATION

Figure C.-2: Metric Performance - EBEAS

CHAPTER C. EVALUATION

C.1 METRIC PERFORMANCES

CHAPTER C. EVALUATION

C.2 Full Direct Comparison

Figure C.-4: Full Direct comparison - Production Cell

Figure C.-3: Direct comparison - EBEAS

C.3 Kendall Tau Correlation

Table C.1: Full Correlation of Metric Candidates - Production Cell

	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7E	R7H	R2S	R3S	R4S	R5S	R6S	R7ES	R7HS
R1	1														
R2	0.0782	1													
R3	0.0865	0.9374	1												
R4	0.0953	0.8652	0.9161	1											
R5	0.1005	0.6539	0.6655	0.6415	1										
R6	0.1467	0.6961	0.7299	0.7388	0.631	1									
R7E	-0.0597	0.3173	0.3456	0.3716	0.2737	0.3891	1								
R7H	0.1491	0.6954	0.7314	0.739	0.6299	1	0.3959	1							
R2S	0.083	1	0.9385	0.8638	0.6589	0.6934	0.3252	0.6917	1						
R3S	0.0886	0.9376	1	0.9166	0.6665	0.7388	0.3462	0.7289	0.9384	1					
R4S	0.0921	0.8646	0.9167	1	0.6399	0.7366	0.3721	0.7402	0.8656	0.9166	1				
R5S	0.0957	0.6623	0.6691	0.6443	0.9283	0.632	0.2872	0.6345	0.6657	0.6706	0.6435	1			
R6S	0.11	0.5851	0.6204	0.6294	0.5297	0.7962	0.3579	0.8023	0.5919	0.619	0.6298	0.5318	1		
R7ES	-0.0578	0.3026	0.3252	0.3528	0.2683	0.3922	0.9572	0.3758	0.3037	0.3174	0.3538	0.2863	0.3521	1	
R7HS	0.1142	0.5868	0.6256	0.6337	0.5327	0.7967	0.3526	0.7952	0.5914	0.6197	0.6291	0.5364	0.9763	0.3427	1

Table C.2: Full Correlation of Metric Candidates - EBEAS

	R1	R2	R3	R4	R5	R6	R7E	R7H	R2S	R3S	R4S	R5S	R6S	R7ES	R7HS
R1	1														
R2	0.0271	1													
R3	0.0595	0.8832	1												
R4	0.0699	0.8179	0.9249	1											
R5	-	-	-	-	1										
R6	0.1699	0.5606	0.6272	0.6318	-	1									
R7E	0.1104	0.5212	0.5458	0.5421	-	0.6445	1								
R7H	0.1756	0.5653	0.6229	0.6324	-	1	0.6406	1							
R2S	0.0321	1	0.8807	0.8153	-	0.561	0.5259	0.5622	1						
R3S	0.0605	0.8846	0.9894	0.9214	-	0.6252	0.5434	0.6207	0.8866	1					
R4S	0.061	0.8212	0.9275	0.9856	-	0.6351	0.5495	0.6401	0.818	0.927	1				
R5S	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1			
R6S	0.09	0.4484	0.5005	0.5049	-	0.6642	0.485	0.6638	0.4461	0.5019	0.5018	-	1		
R7ES	0.0942	0.4568	0.4634	0.4599	-	0.5651	0.8537	0.5635	0.4576	0.4643	0.4655	-	0.4321	1	
R7HS	0.0883	0.4526	0.501	0.4964	-	0.6661	0.4769	0.6603	0.443	0.5013	0.5089	-	0.9258	0.4203	1